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Meeting: 1514th meeting (December 2024) (DH)

Communication from an NGO (Res Publica) (14/10/2024) concerning the case of Besnik Cani v. Albania (Application No. 37474/20) (appendices are available at the Secretariat upon request).

Information made available under Rule 9.2 of the Rules of the Committee of Ministers for the supervision of the execution of judgments and of the terms of friendly settlements.

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Réunion : 1514^e réunion (décembre 2024) (DH)

Communication d'une ONG (Res Publica) (14/10/2024) relative à l'affaire Besnik Cani c. Albanie (requête n° 37474/20) (des annexes sont disponibles auprès du Secrétariat sur demande) **[anglais uniquement]**

Informations mises à disposition en vertu de la Règle 9.2 des Règles du Comité des Ministres pour la surveillance de l'exécution des arrêts et des termes des règlements amiables.

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DGI

14 OCT. 2024

SERVICE DE L'EXECUTION
DES ARRETS DE LA CEDH

Tirana, 14 October 2024

Communication by the Albanian NGO Res Publica

Under Rule 9.2 of the Rules of the Committee of Ministers for the supervision of the
execution of judgments and of the terms of friendly settlements

in the cases of

Besnik Cani v. Albania

(application no. 37474/20, judgment of 4 October 2022)

Sevdari v. Albania

(application no. 40662/19, judgment of 13 March 2023)

“ [...] It must be remembered, however, that such radical solution [the vetting process] would be ill-advised in normal conditions, since it creates enormous tensions within the judiciary, destabilises its work, augments public distrust in the judiciary, diverts the judges’ attention from their normal tasks, and, **as every extraordinary measure, creates a risk of the capture of the judiciary by the political force which controls the process.**”¹

“[...] The first instance court had the obligation to provide arguments regarding

- in what way would the provision of complete information on the entity that sponsored the accommodation of the [Independent Qualification Commission] Commissioners in a hotel, harm the public interest, at a time when this interest is not ascertained to have suffered any harm until now, from the systematic publication of several years of data of judges of the Republic of Albania, including their accommodation in hotels; such publication even having been considered to serve as an instrument for restoring the public’s confidence in justice;
- on what basis should the transparency standard, already implemented in the context of the vetting process of judges in office, not also be applied to the Commissioners who are quasi-judges”²

Introduction

1. This communication by the Albanian NGO Res Publica (hereinafter: “Res Publica”) is addressed to the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe, in accordance with Rule 9.2 of the Rules of the Committee of Ministers, in the context of the supervision of the execution of the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights (hereinafter: “the Court”) in the cases of *Besnik Cani v. Albania* and *Sevdari v. Albania*. These cases concern:

- The lack of remedies to challenge the irregular appointment of vetting bodies’ members during the vetting proceedings (*Besnik Cani v. Albania*) and
- The effectiveness of remedies to challenge the irregular appointment of vetting bodies’ members both during the vetting proceedings and after their conclusion, as well as the disproportionate nature of the measure of her dismissal, on account of her failure to prove the lawful origin of income representing a relatively small percentage of the total amount of her family’s income (*Sevdari v. Albania*).

¹ Venice Commission, *Draft Interim Opinion on the Draft Constitutional Amendments on the Judiciary of Albania*, [CDL\(2015\)052](#), 4 December 2015, paragraph 98. Emphasis added.

² Administrative Appeals Court of Tirana, judgment 36/2024, page 44. The case concerned a challenge by the Independent Qualifications Commission [IQC] against the decision by the Right to Information and Personal Data Protection Commissioner to publish the full text of a sponsorship agreement whereby a company funded a work-related event organized by the IQC. The Appeals Court ultimately held that the first instance court had not provided convincing answers to these two questions and ordered the full disclosure of the agreement. The case will be referred to at length below.

2. The present communication aims to assist the Committee of Ministers in its examination of the execution of the above-mentioned judgments. It contains findings based on Res Publica's long-standing engagement in carrying out research on and monitoring the implementation of the vetting process, including by means of submitting numerous amicus curiae briefs in the majority of vetting-related cases that have been communicated to the Albanian Government.³ At the same time, and in the interest of full disclosure, one of the authors of the present submission is representing before the Court a number of applicants complaining about their unlawful dismissal following the vetting proceedings against them; should there be a critical comment regarding such a decision by the Special Appeal Chamber (hereinafter: "SAC") and not a mere reference to or reproduction of excerpts from the relevant decision, this fact will be indicated explicitly. Be that as it may, and in order to avoid any hint of personal bias, references to such cases shall be kept to a minimum.

3. This submission effectively constitutes an attempt to address the issues and questions raised by the two quotes above, namely to which extent the vetting process in Albania might have in fact undermined instead of strengthened the rule of law, and whether it has introduced double standards in the assessment of already serving judges and prosecutors and vetting bodies' members. **Section I** contains an overview of the Court's holdings in the aforementioned two judgments, together with a summary and a critical overview of the respondent Government's respective action plans / reports and related up to date information; it will also briefly compare them to action plans and reports adopted in the aftermath of judgments issued against other states and raising similar issues. **Section II** provides an overview of SAC's case law on the issue of review of the lawfulness of the vetting bodies' members, focusing in particular on SAC *post Besnik Cani* and *post Sevdari* case law. It will also assess whether SAC, to date, has meaningfully sought to abide by the crystalline ratio of these judgments and, if not, what are the implications of its refusal to do so. **Section III** will attempt to place Res Publica's findings under the previous section in the context of the relevant tests regarding the lawfulness of the appointment of judicial officials developed by the Court and the Court of Justice of the European Union (hereinafter: "CJEU") in their jurisprudence. **Section IV** will provide a critical assessment of a key component of the vetting process in Albania, namely a critical assessment of the work of the European Union and United States funded International Monitoring Operation (IMO) and will seek to assess whether in its work it has managed to strike a balance between, on the one hand, ensuring the integrity of the vetting process, and the successful implementation of the vetting process as a flagship rule of law project (the failure of which would incur significant reputational damage on a number of stakeholders) on the other. **Section V** contains information regarding similar vetting processes in other countries that never got off the ground and vetting processes that are currently under implementation in other countries facing similar rule of law challenges; the latter will be compared to the vetting scheme being implemented in Albania. **Section VI** will seek to briefly position the vetting in the wider political and rule of law context in Albania and attempt to answer the question if the Albanian Government can be objectively considered to be truly committed to strengthening the rule of law or are in fact merely paying lip-service to it. These sections are followed by Res Publica's conclusions and recommendations to the Committee of Ministers. For ease of reference, the most important documents (or excerpts thereof) that will be referred to, have been unofficially translated into English and are attached to the present submission.

³ See *Xhoxhaj v. Albania*, no. 15227/19, §§ 276 - 279, 9 February 2021. More recently, Res Publica filed amicus curiae briefs in the cases of *Hoxha v. Albania* and *Dedja v. Albania*, nos. 16701/19 and 32489/19, communicated to the Albanian Government on 31 May 2023.

I. Court's holdings in *Besnik Cani v. Albania* and *Sevdari v. Albania*; Albanian Government's undertakings as set out in their action plans / reports and comparison of said plans / reports with ones undertaking by other respondent Governments in similar cases

4. In *Besnik Cani v. Albania*, the Court took note that ordinary courts did not have power to review the lawfulness of former SAC member L.D.'s appointment but could only review his criminal liability (op. cit., § 94). It considered that it was the state authorities' duty to ensure that his candidateness for the position of SAC member met the statutory criteria (ibid, § 105) and that his fitness for office constituted a fundamental rule regarding the appointment of SAC members (ibid, § 108). The Court also took note of the Albanian Government's argument that, unlike Constitutional Court judges, there was no provision regulating the early termination of a SAC member on grounds that they did not meet the eligibility criteria, and that the Constitutional Court in its judgment held that it was up to SAC to ensure full respect of the applicant's Article 6 rights in the context of the vetting proceedings against him. It also implicitly criticized SAC for not reasoning its refusal to apply the Constitutional Court Act regarding its members' mandate to SAC's members (ibid, §109. 112). Under Article 46, the Court did not consider it imperative for all cases in which former SAC member L.D. had sat to be reopened (ibid., §144). Regarding individual measures, the Court took note of the Government's position that "there **might** [emphasis added]" be a legal avenue for Mr. Cani to reopen the proceedings in his case, on the basis of Articles 494(ë) of the Code of Civil Procedure and 71/c Constitutional Court Act. The Court left it at the applicant's choice to request such a reopening (ibid, § 148).

5. In *Sevdari v Albania*, the Court rejected the applicant's complaints regarding the unlawful appointment of the same former SAC member (L.D.), noting first, that she had failed to challenge it during the vetting proceedings against her – even though she was aware of his irregular appointment- and second, that even after the conclusion of the proceedings, she did not file a request for the exceptional review of the proceedings, in which she could have argued that L.D. had been unlawfully appointed. The Court also considered that, following the Constitutional Court judgment in the *Besnik Cani* case, the applicant should have brought forward these arguments before SAC thus giving it an opportunity to revisit its stance on this issue (op. cit., §§ 109-112). Regarding the income which she could not justify, the Court noted that some of it had been earned by her spouse before their marriage (and before the applicant had been appointed as a prosecutor) while for some other income streams, the Court noted that its licit origin had not been in doubt. It also noted that the income she could not justify constituted "a relatively small percentage of the total amount of spousal income" (ibid, §§91-93). The Court did not indicate any general measures under Article 46 but left the issue upon the respondent state, subject to the Committee of Ministers' supervision (ibid, § 142). Regarding individual measures, and in light of its findings in *Besnik Cani* as to the possible existence of an extraordinary remedy, it indicated that the applicant could request the reopening of the proceedings in her case (ibid, § 154).

6. Res Publica considers that the Court's holdings are clear. At least after the delivery of the judgment in *Besnik Cani*, assessees should have a right to challenge the lawfulness of the appointment of vetting bodies' members before the SAC. Similarly, at least after the delivery of the judgment in *Sevdari*, assessees in principle should have the right to ask SAC for the reopening of the proceedings in their case on the basis of Article 494 of the Code of Civil Procedure (Annex 1). Additionally, SAC should pay more attention as to the date when an

income whose licit origin is in doubt was created, and examine if said income constitutes a certain percentage of the assessee's total income – an indirect reference to Article 61(1) of the Vetting Act (ibid) whereby there is cause for an assessee's dismissal if their declared assets of the person being vetted were greater than twice the value of the assets obtained with taxed income (see *Sevdari*, op. cit., § 26, 28).

7. The Albanian Government's action plans / reports contain virtually no information regarding these holdings; in its Action Report on the individual and general measures implemented in the aftermath of the *Besnik Cani* judgment, the Albanian Government considered that the "general measure" of suspending and removing from office former SAC member L.D., together with the publication and dissemination of the judgment, constituted adequate measures. It also noted that the applicant in *Besnik Cani* had yet to file a request for reopening of his case with SAC, as indicated by the Court, and called upon the Committee of Ministers to close its supervision.⁴ In its further communication dated 9 September 2024, the Albanian Government criticised once again Mr. Cani for failing to file a request for the reopening of the proceedings in his case before SAC but filing a request for reinstatement with the High Prosecutorial Council which was a remedy not indicated by the Court, and, noting that the relevant time limit for so doing had lapsed, effectively considered that he had waived his right to do so.⁵ The Albanian Government submissions contain no reference to SAC post-*Cani* case law, in which SAC continues to refuse to review the lawfulness of the vetting bodies' appointment; equally importantly, the submissions contains no reference to SAC decision JR 12/2024 (Annex 2), adopted on 19 April 2024, in which SAC itself acknowledged that it could not form a fresh panel to review requests for reopening under Article 494 *et seq.* While admittedly SAC held that it could grant requests for reopening of the proceedings only under Article 494(ë) of the Code of Civil Procedure (i.e. following a Court judgment), the impossibility of forming a fresh panel, as required under Article 494, means that it cannot review the merits of any case, with SAC noting that this impossibility did not arise by accident but it was the will of the legislator to *preclude* the reopening of vetting cases (op. cit., § 12.8) – unless the Albanian Government insist that essentially the same SAC panel that originally reviewed Mr. Cani's case should review the merits of his case in the context of the reopened proceedings, thereby violating his Article 6 rights a second time.

8. In this connection, Res Publica would like to highlight another issue, one that has not been raised by the Government; under Albanian law, the termination of the mandate of officials such as the High Justice Inspector or the General Prosecutor on grounds of irregular appointment have retroactive effect from the date of appointment (Annex 1, article by former Constitutional Court judge Mr. Sokol Berberi) and decisions issued by courts the panels of which have been formed irregularly are absolutely null and void (*absolutisht të pavlefshëme*) (Annex 1, Supreme Court Joint Benches decision no 2/2011) and thus should be considered null and void from their inception (*Topallaj v. Albania*, no 32913/03, § 52, 21 April 2016). As a result, and in view of former SAC member L.D.'s participation in the SAC panel that reviewed Mr. Cani's and other assessee's cases, it is highly likely that, on the basis of domestic law, **all** SAC decisions in which Mr. L.D. sat are tainted by absolute invalidity and should be tried anew (and not merely reopened). While admittedly the Court did not indicate such a drastic course of action in its *Besnik Cani* judgment, it is recalled that it is hardly the Court's role to indicate to the respondent

⁴ Albanian Government, [On the execution of the judgment of the European Court of Human Rights in the application no. 37474/20 "Besnik Cani v. Albania"](#), 12 September 2023.

⁵ Albanian Government, [On the execution of the judgment of the European Court of Human Rights in the application no. 37474/20 "Besnik Cani v. Albania"](#), 9 September 2024.

Government how to interpret and apply its domestic law (*Thanza v. Albania*, no. 41047/19, § 150, 4 July 2023). Res Publica finds rather telling the respondent Government's "omission" to engage with this issue – at the time when, as it will be seen below, States facing far less pressing rule of law issues have done so, regardless of whether such a course of action has been indicated by the Court and of the impact it might have on their judiciaries. It is also noted that the Polish Supreme Court's joined Chambers, in their interpretative Resolution of 23 January 2020 (case no. BSA I-4110-1/20), considered, among others, that any judgment issued by a formation with the participation of judges appointed to the Disciplinary Chamber of the Supreme Court under the 2017 Act on the Supreme Court should be considered as having been issued by an unlawfully composed court "irrespective of the date of such judgments" and therefore the finding had retroactive effect; of note that under Article 46, the Court held that a potential general measure could be applying the aforementioned resolution (*Advance Pharma sp. z o.o v. Poland* (no. 1469/20, § 127, 365, 3 February 2022).

9. While on the same topic, Res Publica also notes that both Messrs L.D. and A.H. (another former SAC member who was sentenced for concealing his property and not meeting the eligibility criteria amply qualify as "usurpers" (someone less charitably inclined would call them "imposters") whose decisions have to be invalidated (Opinion of Advocate General Sharpston, Cases C-542/18 RX-II and C-543/18 RX-II, *Simpson and HG v European Commission*, § 100, 12 September 2019). Res Publica notes that whereas in *Guðmundur Andri Ástráðsson v. Iceland* [GC] (no. 26374/18, 1 December 2020) the judges concerned were not responsible for their irregular appointment (they had not misrepresented their skills or qualifications), Messrs L.D. and A.H. effectively lied before the Parliament which, to boot, can be considered as having constructive knowledge of their ineligibility (particularly so in the case of Mr. L.D.) yet proceeded to appoint them anyway, even though, as the Court noted in *Besnik Cani*, it fell on the state authorities (and, Res Publica would add, the International Monitoring Operation (hereinafter: "IMO")) to verify that the candidates satisfied the relevant eligibility criteria (op.cit., § 105).

10. Turning to the *Sevdari* judgment execution, the respondent Government merely noted in their action plan that they had translated and disseminated the judgment and informed the Committee of Ministers that the applicant had filed with SAC a request for reopening of the proceedings.⁶ The action plan contains no references to relevant *post-Sevdari* SAC jurisprudence regarding either the effectiveness of the extraordinary remedy prescribed by Article 494 Code of Civil Procedure or the application of Article 61(1) Vetting Act. Regarding the former, as noted above, SAC has made it clear that unless the Court indicates the reopening of the proceedings in its judgment, then SAC will not, on any other ground foreseen under Article 494 Code of Civil Procedure, reopen the proceedings (Annex 2, § 14.1, 17). Regarding the latter, and to this day, SAC has never applied Article 61(1) Vetting Act to either dismiss or confirm in duty an assessee. In fact, there is evidence of the *lengths* at which SAC will go in order to *not* refer to Article 61(1); in a recent judgment in which SAC confirmed in duty an assessee even though it identified an unjustified deficit of 2.386.496 ALL in the assessee's total income, it considered that despite the fact that there was no evidence that said income was lawful, there was evidence that the sources of that income were of licit origin and did not warrant the assessee's dismissal, who was confirmed in duty because he did not violate Article 61(3) Vetting Act rather than on the basis Article 61(1) (Annex 1, JR 20/2023). While Res Publica fully agrees with SAC's decision in that case, it can only speculate as to why SAC has not

⁶ Albanian Government, [On the execution of the judgment of the European Court of Human Rights in the application no. 40662/19 "Sevdari v. Albania"](#), 9 October 2023

adopted a similar approach in the past as well as to SAC's insistence in refusing to apply Article 61(1) Vetting Act, thus effectively abolishing it in practice – a concern raised also by the IMO Observer in *Sevdari* who forcefully argued in favour of its application (op. cit., § 28). It will only note that Article 61(1) Vetting Act was meant to be a key safeguard for assessees given the widespread informality in transactions and close family ties in Albania (which could make impossible identifying the exact origin of amounts of money) and that it is the only characteristic of the Albanian vetting scheme that has been emulated in the vetting scheme currently under implementation in Moldova⁷ - which curiously enough is not being applied in Albania. As to the difference applying one article over the other would make, the *Sevdari* judgment bears ample testament to it: under Article 61(1) Vetting Act, Ms. Sevdari would be almost automatically confirmed in duty under the property criterion (as both an SAC minority member and the IMO Observer noted). Under Article 61(3) Vetting Act, she could be (and was) dismissed. In other words, Article 61(3) Vetting Act appears to grant SAC more latitude in deciding whether to dismiss or confirm an assessee in duty, by considering the asset declaration inaccurate. On a wider note, it is also very likely that SAC, rather belatedly, realised that applying Article 61(1) Vetting Act would lead to numerous confirmations, something that could, among certain circles, be considered as an indictment of the vetting scheme; as it will be seen below, the success of the vetting scheme seems to be gauged primarily on the basis of the number of dismissals.

11. Turning to individual measures, Ms. Sevdari filed a request for reopening the proceedings with SAC; her request was granted and she has returned to duty. Nevertheless it took more than one full year for her to be confirmed in duty, even though the outcome of the proceedings was, given the Court's judgment,⁸ all but pre-ordained, and even though due to the number of vacancies in the prosecution service, the reinstatement of an experienced prosecutor should have been fast-tracked; by way of example, in *Goryaynova v. Ukraine* (no. 41572/09, 8 October 2020) the applicant, a prosecutor who had been dismissed, was reinstated in 7 months. Similarly, in *Sorbalo v. Republic of Moldova* (dec) (no. 1210/10, 31 January 2023) the applicant was reinstated also within 7 months.

12. Moreover, it is rather strange that SAC, in confirming the applicant in duty, would premise its decision on Article 494 Civil Procedure Code, a provision introduced in 2008 and aimed at allowing ordinary jurisdiction domestic courts, including the Supreme Court, to reopen proceedings following a judgment by the Court, rather than the provision pertaining explicitly to the Constitutional Court set out in the Constitutional Court Act as amended in 2016. Res Publica recalls that the Court has been rather critical of SAC's failure to invoke the provisions of the Constitution regarding the mandate of Constitutional Court judges when assessing the lawfulness of the appointment of SAC members (*Besnik Cani*, op. cit., § 112); SAC has not advanced any good reason as to why it did not premise its decision on Article 71/c Constitutional Court Act (Annex 1); it is, after all, a chamber of the Constitutional Court and its members have the status of the Constitutional Court judge. Res Publica also notes that due to the impossibility of forming a fresh panel, her request for reopening was heard by a panel in which three SAC members that sat in the original panel took part. While in principle the

⁷ Thus under Article 11(3) of [Law No. 252/2023](#) *On the external evaluation of judges and prosecutors and amendments of some regulatory acts*, an assessee will not be deemed to meet the financial integrity criterion if the unjustified income during the last 12 years is higher than 20 average salaries for 2023; according to information received by Res Publica, should the unjustified income be higher, the assessee will not be automatically dismissed but then they will be invited to adduce evidence as to its lawful origin.

⁸ Which was however put in question by the Public Commissioner who, essentially ignoring the Court's judgment, ultimately asked in the reopened proceedings that the applicant's dismissal be upheld.

applicant could have requested their recusal, the fact that no fresh panel could be formed would lead to the suspension of her case (and her reinstatement) *sine die* (see *Catană c. République de Moldova*, no. 43237/13, §§48-49, 21 February 2023). Her decision therefore not to raise this issue – which in any case SAC should have raised of its own motion, as it was aware of the impossibility of allocating the case to a fresh formation (Annex 2, § 12.8) – is understandable.⁹

13. In light of the shortcomings in the execution of the two judgments referred to above, Res Publica considers it would be instructive to examine how two other respondent Governments, faced with similar challenges in the field of rule of law, acted in the aftermath of two respective judgments against them.

14. Thus following the Court's judgment in *Ástráðsson*, the Government of Iceland set up a Court of Reopening of Judicial Proceedings; all interested parties, including the applicant in that case, could at any time (since there were no time limits) apply to have his case reopened (even though neither a reopening nor any general measures were indicated by the Court under Article 46). Even before the Grand Chamber judgment was delivered, the Minister of Justice who carried out the unlawful appointment resigned and the four judges that were unlawfully appointed to the Court of Appeal withdrew from taking part in its deliberations. In the new appointment process, the Minister of Justice did not deviate from the recommendations of the Evaluation Committee. The four candidates who should have been appointed at the Court of Appeal but were not received both pecuniary and non-pecuniary damages.¹⁰

15. Following the Court's judgment of *Xero Flor w Polsce sp. z o.o. v. Poland* (no. 4907/18, 7 May 2021), and even though the Court in its judgment did not indicate any general measures under Article 46 the Polish Government took a number of measures, such as annulling the appointment of Constitutional Court judges. It would appear that the judgments they issued can be challenged since they are considered invalid and without legal effects.¹¹ It is recalled that the Committee of Ministers, by means of a sternly worded interim resolution, expressed its regret of the Constitutional Court's decision to find that the Court's judgment in *Xero Flor* was contrary to the Polish Constitution and therefore refuse to execute it.¹²

16. Two Council of Europe member states facing rule of law challenges of a totally different magnitude (Iceland, a lower one and Poland, a higher one) than that faced by Albania took a series of far-reaching and particularly onerous general measures, not in order to execute the relevant Court's judgments (as the Court did not indicate such measures) but primarily in order, in Res Publica's opinion, to restore their respective citizenries' tarnished trust in their judicial systems. This is precisely what the Albanian Government **did not do** following *Besnik Cani* and *Sevdari*, opting instead for a purely superficial execution of these judgments, at a time when Albanian society's positive views as to the reformed justice system's positive impact on

⁹ Res Publica notes that the Court did not hold against an applicant her failure to request the recusal of more than half the members of the Superior Council for Judges; *Catană c. République de Moldova*, op. cit., § 49.

¹⁰ Icelandic Government, [Action Report for the following Grand Chamber case: Guðmundur Andri Ástráðsson v. Iceland](#) (application No. 26374/18, judgment of 1 December 2020), 15 December 2021.

¹¹ Polish Government, [Communication from the authorities concerning the cases of Xero Flor w Polsce sp. z o.o. v. Poland \(Application no. 4907/18\)](#), 26 June 2024.

¹² Committee of Ministers, [Interim Resolution CM/ResDH\(2023\)142](#) Execution of the judgment of the European Court of Human Rights - Xero Flor w Polsce sp. z o.o. against Poland, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 7 June 2023 at the 1468th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies

the country are diminishing.¹³ As if this were not enough, and as it will be seen in the following paragraphs, SAC continues to refuse to abide by the Court's clear holdings in its case law following the adoption of these two judgments, further undermining the authority and the proper functioning of the Court.

II. Overview of SAC's case law on the existence of domestic remedies for challenging the lawfulness of the vetting bodies' members post *Besnik Cani* and post *Sevdari*: is the SAC mightier than the Court?

17. Res Publica considers that due to both the method of their members' appointment and the numerous shortcomings in the selection and appointment processes, the vetting bodies – and in particular SAC which is the final and only judicial instance in the vetting proceedings - do not, for the purposes of Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights (the Convention) constitute “tribunals established by law”.¹⁴ While admittedly this issue was not raised in either the *Besnik Cani* or *Sevdari* judgments, a corollary (namely the existence of remedies to challenge the appointment of vetting bodies' members during or after the vetting proceedings) was. As a result, Res Publica considers it important to delve into whether the selection and appointment processes were regular. This is because, if any shortcomings were to be identified, then assessee should have a right to challenge them. If, on the other hand, these processes were accompanied by ironclad safeguards that were respected in practice, then any relevant claim put forward by an assessee should be considered unmeritorious.

18. The question whether IQC/SAC constitute, on the basis of the selection and appointment of their members, “tribunals established by law” has already been raised by a number of assessee during the re-evaluation proceedings against them. Nevertheless, while SAC has been quick to answer that question in the affirmative, it has never given a properly reasoned answer nor advanced any persuasive grounds to that end, as evidenced by the different responses it has provided in relation to those claims. Thus SAC has at times held the lawfulness of the vetting bodies' members appointment has been authoritatively established by the Court in its *Xhoxhaj v Albania* (no 15227/19, 9 February 2021) judgment, by the Constitutional Court in its judgment no. 2/2017 and by the Venice Commission. It has also argued that other bodies / institutions involved in their selection and appointment (such as the Ombudsperson, the International Monitoring Operation (IMO) and the Parliament) have ensured that the relevant criteria were met (see e.g. Annex 3, JR 36/2021, § 22). In other cases, SAC has argued that in light of the extraordinary and time-limited nature of the revaluation process, allowing the challenging of the appointment of the members of the vetting bodies would undermine the revaluation scheme's implementation, particularly if said challenges were launched well after the establishment and functioning of the vetting bodies (Annex 3, JR 38/2023, § 15.2.1; JR 43/2022, § 14.2.iv). Last, in other cases, SAC has argued its jurisdiction as set out by the Constitution does not include the mandate of reviewing the lawfulness of the appointment of the vetting bodies' members (Annex 3, JR 10/2022, §6.2.a) – a response that clearly comes into conflict with the previous two. In the following paragraphs, Res Publica will seek to

¹³ Thus according to the IDM [Trust in Governance: Opinion Poll 2023](#), published in May 2024, 50.2% of the respondents agreed that the judicial reform had a positive impact on the country while 44.9% disagreed; in the [2020 edition](#) of the same report, only 31% of the respondent disagreed with that statement and 16.2% responded that they did not know. These percentages are a far cry from the 90% which looked forward to the implementation of vetting in 2017; Prime Minister's Office, [The vetting will be done!](#), 25 March 2017.

¹⁴ Res Publica recalls that Court Judge Serghides has also taken the view, which he has expressed on all vetting cases against Albania he has participated in, that both IQC and SAC do not qualify as tribunals under Article 6. See dissenting opinion in *Xhoxhaj v. Albania*, op. cit., § 17.

address the well-foundedness of these three strands of responses by SAC and assess whether they are compatible with the Court's holdings in the *Besnik Cani* and *Sevdari* judgments.

1. Whether the European Court of Human Rights, the Constitutional Court and the Venice commission have endorsed the selection and appointment processes for the members of the re-evaluation bodies

19. Regarding the first argument put forward by SAC, Res Publica notes that the Court in *Xhoxhaj* explicitly **declined to assess the method of appointment** of the vetting bodies' members (op. cit., § 296) and therefore any impact shortcomings in their appointment might have had in the fairness of the proceedings. Nevertheless, this is *precisely* what the Court did and where it premised its finding of violation of Article 6 in *Guðmundur Andri Ástráðsson v. Iceland* [GC] (no. 26374/18, 1 December 2020), which preceded *Xhoxhaj*. Moreover, the Court did the same in two cases subsequent to *Xhoxhaj* and dealing with similar issues, namely those of *Xero Flor w Polsce sp. z o.o. v. Poland* (no. 4907/18, 7 May 2021) and *Reczkowicz v Poland* (no. 43447/19, § 235, 22 July 2021). In the former, the Court reviewed in detail the appointment process of the newly installed judges to the Constitutional Court, took note of the significant controversy around it, concluded that their appointment was in breach of domestic law and applied the *Ástráðsson* three-tiered test (ibid., § 254, 257, 263, 270, 276). In the latter, the Court also reviewed the appointment procedure of the judges (noting that in light of its importance, this issue called for strict scrutiny) of the newly constituted Disciplinary Chamber of the Supreme Court (a body similar to SAC), sharply criticized the Constitutional Court's decision upholding the lawfulness of their appointment, and applied the *Ástráðsson* three-tiered test.

20. Somewhat interestingly, SAC has considered that the *Ástráðsson* three-tiered test is either complied with in the case of the members of the vetting bodies (Annex 3, JR 43/2022, § 14.2.iii) – without however providing any arguments warranting this conclusion - or that, since all political parties agreed to the method of appointment and in fact appointed the members of the vetting bodies, then the requirements under the test were met (Annex 3, JR 3/2023, § 10.1.6) – a rather novel interpretation of *Ástráðsson*.

21. It is therefore interesting that applying the *Ástráðsson* three-tiered test in *Besnik Cani v. Albania*, the Court **did find** a violation of Article 6 regarding the appointment of SAC member L.D.; while the latter's appointment was not reviewed directly by domestic courts (which assessed his criminal liability), the Court noted that contextual findings from the criminal proceedings could be used to assess whether his failure to meet the eligibility criteria constituted a “minister breach of domestic law” (*Besnik Cani*, op. cit., § 94). It is of some interest in this respect that another former SAC member, Mr. A.H., has been found guilty of false declaration and his judicial mandate has been terminated. In other words, out of the nine (main and alternate) members of SAC, two have not only been appointed blatantly unlawfully and thus incurred disciplinary liability but have also been found guilty in criminal proceedings.

22. Nevertheless, Res Publica contends that, quite apart from the individual liability (disciplinary or criminal) that SAC members might incur, the main problem in the establishment of the two vetting bodies, and particularly of SAC, stems from the **selection and appointment processes** themselves, which present a series of shortcomings that have a direct impact on the lawfulness of the appointment of their members.

23. The first such shortcoming consists of the lack of a ranking system of the successful candidates, namely those candidates who were included in “List A”. Given the absence of such a system (which existed in the *Ástráðsson* case and the unreasoned deviation from which led to a finding of violation of Article 6) and contrary to the Court’s repeated calls to limit the discretion of the legislature in issues relating to the selection, appointment and promotion of judicial officials (*Bilgen v Turkey*, no. 1571/07, § 63, 9 March 2021; *Kartal v. Türkiye*, no. 54699/14, § 82, 26 March 2024), the Albanian Parliament had unfettered discretion in two respects: first, it could appoint whomever it pleased from “List A” without needing to provide even some basic reasoning or explain the criteria that led it to its decision to appoint one shortlisted candidate over the other; the Court has been critical of appointment processes where the appointing body enjoys a large margin of discretion and does not have to premise its decision on well-defined criteria (see *Catană c. République de Moldova*, no. 43237/13, § 80, 82, 21 February 2023; *Ástráðsson*, op. cit., § 234 section (ii)). To put this in perspective, the seminal *Ástráðsson* would not have come about had the relevant legislation not provided for a system of ranking of shortlisted candidates. Res Publica also notes that the Venice Commission is increasingly calling for the introduction of ranking in the assessment of judicial officials in non-vetting contexts.¹⁵ If nothing else, the need for such a system is *higher* in the context of a vetting scheme, if only in order to limit the executive / legislature’s discretion in appointing its favored candidates, given that, if vetting is truly called for on account of the extent of corruption in the judiciary, then automatically concerns arise as to whether corruption has seeped in parliamentary life, given that corruption, like nature, abhors a vacuum. Indeed, Res Publica would note that, *precisely* due to the extraordinary nature of vetting (both in terms of the challenges that can lead to the decision to implement it and the risks of the executive using vetting as a means of weeding out undesirable judicial officials) and the dearth of relevant standards,¹⁶ what would make sense is the stringent adherence to the already existing standards on the independence of the judiciary and the stronger engagement of the judiciary councils.¹⁷

24. Second, under Article C § 8 of the Annex to the Albanian Constitution and Article 8 § 3 of the Vetting Law (Annex 1) Parliament could, subject only to a requirement for a 2/3 majority among the members of the ad hoc Parliamentary Commission), appoint even candidates who did not meet the selection criteria and were included in “List B” (i.e. the not shortlisted

¹⁵ Venice Commission, [Opinion no. 1001/20210](#), *Georgia: Opinion on the draft Organic Law amending the Organic Law on Common Courts*, CDL-AD(2020)021, 8 October 2020, paragraphs 15, 18, 33. Thus according to paragraph 15: “In order for the best candidates to be presented to Parliament, the Venice Commission had recommended abolishing decisions by secret ballot, publishing information regarding the qualifications of the candidates, evaluating the candidates on the basis of objective criteria, producing a pool of suitable candidates, ranked according to the scores they had obtained during the evaluation procedure.” See also Venice Commission, [Opinion no. 940/2018](#), *Malta: Opinion on the Constitutional Arrangements and Separation of Powers and the independence of the judiciary and law enforcement*, CDL-AD(2018)028, 17 December 2018, paragraphs 35-37, 44(2) to (5), 145. Thus according to paragraph 145(1): “Judicial vacancies should be announced, an enlarged Judicial Appointments Committee should vet and rank the applicants, including for the position of Chief Justice, and the JAC [Judicial Appointments Committee] should propose candidates directly to the President of Malta for appointment. Dismissals of judges and magistrates should not be made by Parliament.”

¹⁶ Venice Commission, [Opinion no. 1064/2021](#), *Kosovo: Opinion on the concept paper on the vetting of judges and prosecutors and draft amendments to the Constitution*, CDL-AD(2022)011, 20 June 2022, paragraph 13: “Integrity checking and vetting procedures are not explicitly regulated by international instruments. They have, however, been dealt with and commented upon, by soft law instruments and by case law.” CEELI Institute, [Guidelines on Judicial Vetting](#), March 2024, paragraph 6: “International instruments for the independence of the judiciary do not explicitly envisage the vetting process as a measure.”

¹⁷ Consultative Council of European Judges (CCJE), [Opinion no. 24/2021](#), *Evolution of the Councils for the Judiciary and their Role*, November 2021, paragraph 21. It is of interest that whereas CCJE would not be against the vetting of the judicial councils themselves, this should be done by an independent body.

candidates), without being under the obligation to provide even the most rudimentary reasoning for appointing candidates from “List B” when there were more than enough candidates in “List A”. Res Publica recalls that, as the Court has held, the “higher a tribunal was placed in the judicial hierarchy, the more demanding the applicable selection criteria should be” (*Xero Flor w Polsce sp. z o.o. v. Poland*, op.cit., § 244). Parliament was quick to take advantage of its unfettered discretion (*Reczkowicz v. Poland*, op. cit., § 274); SAC member R.G.S. was **twice** found not to meet the relevant selection criteria and was placed in “List B”, yet Parliament appointed her as a member of SAC without providing any reasoning as to why she should be preferred over any of the candidates included in “List A”. It is important to note in this respect that, under the appointment process, unsuccessful candidates who were included in “List A” had no right to challenge the rejection of their candidatures; the existence of judicial remedies in legal officials’ appointment processes is an element that the Court takes into consideration when assessing their lawfulness (*Franz v Germany*, no. 29295/16, § 70, 20 January 2020; *Oktay Alkan v. Türkiye*, no. 24492/21, § 58, 20 June 2023) – an element completely missing from the process of selection of candidates for the three vetting bodies. The importance of such a safeguard would have been crucial in ensuring that any deficiencies in the appointment process would be swiftly addressed and that only meritorious candidates would be appointed; in *Ástráðsson*, the unlawful appointment of the candidates ranking lower than others was established in the context of proceedings brought forward by candidates who, while higher on the list, were not appointed (op. cit., §§67-75, 208). Had it not been for these challenges, it would have been all but impossible for the applicant in *Ástráðsson* first, to realize that there had been shortcomings in the appointment of the judge hearing his case and second, to be in a position to assess whether said shortcomings could have had a bearing on the review of his case.

25. The second shortcoming consists in that neither the Ombudsperson nor the IMO or the Parliament had adequate time to review whether the candidates met the formal eligibility criteria, while each interview before the two ad hoc Parliamentary Commissions did not last for longer than 5-10 minutes,¹⁸ with the questions addressed to the candidates being rather simplistic and hardly allowing for any assessment of their qualities and skills; regarding whether they had been subjected to disciplinary measures that were in force, candidates were asked to provide a self-declaration to the effect (*Besnik Cani*, op. cit., §11) – a rather naïve and poorly thought out measure, if nothing else.

26. The third shortcoming, related to the previous one, is that the institutions in charge of the selection process clearly had no time to review (by requesting relevant documentation from competent state agencies) whether the successful candidates met the relevant criteria (*Besnik Cani*, op. cit., §§ 103-106). As a result, and at the time of writing, two of the nine SAC members have been found to have failed to meet the relevant criteria and have been dismissed, a development that could have been avoided had the competent authorities have carried out a rudimentary background check. Nor are they the only vetting bodies’ members whose appointment has been tainted, as it will be argued below.

¹⁸ It is rather telling that appointment process presents some uncanny similarities with the one of Polish judges criticized by the Commissioner for Human Rights of the Republic of Poland, in this third party submission in *Advance Pharma sp. z o.o v. Poland* (no. 1469/20, 3 February 2022), § 277: “The NCJ [National Council for the Judiciary] had carried out a rudimentary selection process based mostly on the material presented by the candidates themselves and had spent a dozen minutes per interviewed candidate. As a result, the NCJ had recommended only those candidates who were associated with the authorities and had their support.”

27. The fourth shortcoming concerns the direct political interference in the appointment of the vetting bodies' members, a feature that was all but purposefully included in the selection and appointment process. It is none other than one of the independent authorities, namely the Ombudsperson, playing a key role in the candidate selection processes, who found them highly politicized, highlighting particularly the case of SAC member R.G.S. (Annex 4; page 16). Even worse, the other independent – at least on paper – institution involved in the selection of the vetting bodies members, namely the IMO, quite openly favored some candidates at the expense of others, while it has turned a blind eye – and continues to do the same – in relation to others, as it will be seen below.

28. Turning to the third stakeholder in the selection and appointment process, namely the Parliament, Res Publica recalls that the three vetting bodies were set up following a political agreement (the so-called McAllister plus agreement) that explicitly provided for the reaching of an agreement between the two main political parties over the establishment of the vetting bodies – an agreement that has been criticized by OSCE/ODIHR as undermining the rule of law.¹⁹ As the Court has held, members of parliament cannot, by definition, be politically neutral (*Guðmundur Gunnarsson and Magnús Davíð Norðdahl v. Iceland*, nos. 24159/22 and 25751/22, § 82, 16 April 2024). The Court has been critical of procedures where Parliament for example is the only body that can review the appointment of its members, without interested parties having access to judicial or quasi-judicial remedies to contest their non-election (*Mugemangango v. Belgium*, no. 310/15, § 96, 98-99, 137-139, 10 July 2020), *precisely* due to the overly political nature of any decisions taken by Parliament. Res Publica considers that this applies *perforce* when Parliament is the only institution which can decide on the appointment of judicial officials. In *Ástráðsson* the Court took into account the political backdrop of the case and considered the voting *en bloc* of four already serving judges who were not suspected on any wrongdoing but had just scored somewhat lower than other candidates, and held that the applicant's assertions that the Parliament's decision to appoint those four judges was "driven primarily by party political considerations" were not unwarranted (*op.cit.*, § 89, 270, 281). Indeed, a Court judge rather eloquently described the run-up to the Minister's decision to appoint the judges in question as "political horse-trading" (*op. cit.*, Concurring Opinion of Judge Pinto de Albuquerque, §12), similar to how GRECO referred to information regarding negotiations between the main political parties over key judicial appointments (*Lorenzo Bragado and Others v. Spain*, nos. 53193/21 and 5 others, § 62, 22 June 2023). Considering that such negotiations take place in countries facing far fewer rule of law challenges, like Iceland and Spain, it is rather logical to assume that they also took place in Albania in the context of the appointment of the vetting bodies' members – indeed, the reaching of a political agreement under the auspices of the international community *cannot but have involved a fair amount of political horse-trading*. The purely political considerations that influenced the Parliament's decision-making process are amply attested to by its decision to appoint SAC member R.G.S. (although both the Ombudsperson and the IMO **twice** agreed she did not meet the relevant criteria) and Mr. P.S. (appointed as an IQC substitute member) who openly admitted that he was the leader of a political party during the ten years before the vetting process begun (and as such should have been automatically disqualified on the basis of Article

¹⁹ According to OSCE/ODIHR: "...the 18 May political agreement [the McAllister plus agreement that paved the way for the vetting process] was given legal effect at the expense of the rule of law. All amendments were voted on in one day, contrary to the constitutionally prescribed legislative procedure. At odds with OSCE commitments and Council of Europe standards, the process lacked transparency and consultation with stakeholders [...]."; OSCE/ODIHR, Republic of Albania, Parliamentary Elections 25 June 2017, [OSCE/ODIHR Election Observation Mission, Final Report](#), 28 September 2017, page 6.

6(1)(ç) Vetting Act). Given the existence of numerous other candidates in “List A”, the decision to appoint them despite the obvious shortcomings in their candidacies cannot but be attributed to purely political considerations and amply demonstrates the undue influence of the legislative and executive powers on the appointment of judges, which is *per se* incompatible with Article 6§1 of the Convention (*Dolińska - Ficek and Ozimek v. Poland*, nos. 49868/19 and 57511/19, § 349, 8 November 2021).

29. Admittedly, the Court in *Xhoxhaj* held that the appointment of judges by the executive is compatible with the Convention and referred to a series of judgments to that end (op. cit., § 295). Nevertheless these judgments are context-specific and not applicable to the appointment process of the vetting bodies’ members, for the following two reasons. First, because they concerned countries where (with one exception that was not applicable at the time, namely Moldova) there were no concerns regarding the rule of law; it is difficult to see how the fact, if true, that a Parliament in a country not facing a rule of law crisis and mired in corruption can appoint judges can be used as an argument to endorse the appointment of judicial appointment by a Parliament facing such challenges; surely in such countries Parliament should be *the last institution* to be conferred with such discretion. Second, a contextual reading of these judgments would reveal that the respective appointment processes were significantly different from the one in the case of the vetting bodies in Albania. Thus in *Sacilor-Lormines v. France* the Court also reviewed the appearance of impartiality of a member of the Conseil d’Etat on the basis of his subsequent appointment to a high post in the administration and found a violation of Article 6, while in *Thiam v. France* the Court noted that the appointment of judges by the President of the Republic was a mere formality, as it fell on the council for the judiciary to propose the judges to be appointed and the President’s appointment decision could be challenged before the Conseil d’Etat (no. 65411/01, § 69, 9 November 2006, no. 80018/12, §§ 25, 81-82, 18 October 2018, respectively). In *Flux v. Moldova (no. 2)*, the Court took into consideration that the judge in question already enjoyed tenure at the time of his appointment by Parliament to a higher court (no. 31001/03, § 27, 3 July 2007) whereas in *Ástráðsson*, the Court reviewed the political backdrop to the impugned appointment decision, assessed the objectivity of the selection process, and criticized the exercise of unreasoned discretion by the Minister of Justice not to appoint the highest-ranked candidates together with the Parliament’s approval of the Minister’s decision by means of an *en bloc* vote (op. cit., § 264, 270). In **none** of these cases did the Court find that the fully discretionary appointment of judges by Parliament was compatible with the Convention. Moreover, in relation to **none** of the aforementioned countries had the Venice Commission highlighted the existence of links between politicians from across the political spectrum and criminal elements and concluded that, in light of the particular circumstances prevailing in Albania, the introduction of a vetting mechanism for public officials appeared to be serve a “legitimate purpose”.²⁰ From the standpoint of appearances, therefore, conferring unfettered discretion on members of parliament with links to organized crime. who can be expected to vote strictly along party lines for members of the vetting bodies who would in turn vet prosecutors and judges who have either tried cases against them or might do so in the future cannot but give rise to legitimate concerns as to the integrity of their decision-making processes (see by analogy *Guðmundur Gunnarsson and Magnús Davíð Norðdahl v. Iceland*, op. cit., § 86). This would in turn also raise reasonable doubts regarding the integrity and / or political leanings of the candidates that the Parliament ultimately appointed and who would carry out the revaluation process (see by analogy *Ástráðsson*, op. cit., § 239).

²⁰ Venice Commission, Opinion on draft constitutional amendments enabling the vetting of politicians, [CDL-AD\(2018\)034](#), 17 December 2018, paragraphs 17, 52

30. Turning to the Venice Commission's alleged endorsement of IQC/SAC as tribunals established by law, Res Publica notes that this quite simply inaccurate.²¹ It is recalled that the Venice Commission was originally informed that SAC would be a chamber of the High Court and criticized the absolute prohibition of the right to file a constitutional complaint.²² Even though subsequently informed that the SAC was elevated to a chamber of the Constitutional Court, the Venice Commission noted first that it was not asked to address the differences between the three different drafts²³ - and thus clearly did not review, let alone endorse, the last draft that was ultimately adopted. Second, the Venice Commission welcomed that the restriction in the second draft precluding assessees from filing complaints with the Constitutional Court did not appear "in the constitutional text finally adopted" and that consequently the Constitutional Court would be able to review such complaints, as well as review referrals for constitutional review of a vetting legislation provision according to Article 145§2.²⁴ The Constitutional Court, in its judgment no 2/2017, held that the Venice Commission was wrong to consider that a complaint to the Constitutional Court was possible, as the Constitution had explicitly precluded this possibility, providing instead for the right (sic) to file an application with the Court (Annex 1, § 68). The above clearly indicate that the Venice Commission consistently considered that, even though the SAC was a chamber of the Constitutional Court, assessees could still have a right to seize the legitimate Constitutional Court. Its insistence on the possibility for assessees to seize the Constitutional Court is not accidental: the establishment of specialized jurisdictions such as the SAC does not raise any concerns under Article 6 of the Convention as long as they are made up of judges *and / or* their decisions are amenable to judicial review by courts of the standard judicial machinery (*Bahaettin Uzan v. Turkey*, no. 30836/07, § 53, 63, 24 November 2020; *Ali Rıza c. Suisse*, no. 95, no. 74989/11, § 13 July 2021), all the more since assessees under the re-evaluation scheme are forced to undergo vetting before the IQC/SAC and thus no issue of voluntary waiver of their Article 6 rights arises. Nevertheless not only are IQC/SAC not parts of said machinery (as opposed to, for example, the Special Anti-Corruption Structure – SPAK- the judgments of which can be challenged before the Supreme and Constitutional Courts) but SAC in particular, under Article 179§7 of the Constitution, has both original disciplinary jurisdiction (regarding Constitutional Court judges, members of the High Judicial Council/High Prosecutorial Council, the Prosecutor General and the High Justice Inspector) and appellate disciplinary jurisdiction (regarding challenges against decisions of the High Judicial Council/High Prosecutorial Council and the High Justice Inspector imposing disciplinary sanctions against judges, prosecutors and inspectors). It is also an *ad hoc* disciplinary body for members of the vetting institutions under Article 17 Vetting Act. Rather than constituting a specialized jurisdiction *within* the national judicial machinery, SAC is therefore essentially completely autonomous from it and has in fact jurisdiction over disciplinary proceedings against judicial officials, including decisions regarding judicial officials who have already been vetted, without any good reason for such extensive competences having been advanced (unless, for some

²¹ As an aside, Res Publica notes that the Venice Commission has not even endorsed the vetting scheme itself, noting that whether a wide consensus that vetting was necessary constituted adequate grounds for embarking on such an extreme measure was a "question of political necessity and the **Venice Commission is not in a position to pronounce on it**"; Venice Commission, *Interim Opinion on the draft constitutional amendments on the judiciary of Albania*, [CDL-AD\(2015\)045](#), 21 December 2015, paragraph 98; emphasis added.

²² Venice Commission, *Final Opinion on the Revised Draft Constitutional Amendments on the Judiciary*, [CDL-AD\(2016\)009](#), 14 March 2016, paragraphs 63, 65- 66.

²³ Venice Commission, *Amicus Curiae Brief for the Constitutional Court on the Law on the Transitional Re-Evaluation of Judges and Prosecutors (the Vetting Law)*, [CDL-AD\(2016\)036](#), 12 December 2016, paragraph 15.

²⁴ *Ibid*, paragraphs 44-45.

reason, the Albanian Government and its international partners do not trust even vetted judicial officials).

31. While the fact that SAC has been elevated to the most powerful court in Albania is already problematic in and of itself, the main problem for present purposes lies in the fact that, as SAC is operating outside the national judiciary, there is domestically no independent judicial body that can review the selection and appointment of its members, as it will be argued below; indeed, not even itself can review the appointment of its members, something that should have been expected of a apex court (as it is the case for the legitimate Constitutional Court). At present, it should suffice to note that Parliament could, quite simply, follow the approach recommended by the Venice Commission and provide assessees with a right to challenge, even on limited grounds, the appointment of the members of the vetting bodies. There is, for example, no evidence that the situation in Albania was similar to the one obtaining in *Gyulumyan and Others v. Armenia* (dec) that made the abolition of the applicants' right to challenge the termination of their mandate necessary (no. 25240/20, § 84, 7 December 2023). Rather, the Parliament purposefully, and despite the existence of other options as expressly indicated by the Venice Commission (*Sözen c. Türkiye*, no. 73532/16, § 76, 9 April 2024; request for referral pending), decided to exclude the right of assessees to file a complaint with the Constitutional Court, an entitlement that would be particularly crucial in cases where the assessees sought to challenge the lawfulness of the appointment of the IQC/SAC members. It is important to note in this respect that in other countries that are currently implementing similar re-evaluation schemes, such as Moldova, decisions of the vetting bodies – which are not bodies external to the standard national machinery but the judicial councils for prosecutors and judges - are amenable to appeal before national courts – in the case of Moldova, before the Supreme Court of Justice.²⁵

32. Turning to the Constitutional Court, the latter in its judgment no. 2/2017 did not address the apparent misunderstanding under which the Venice Commission labored nor did it seek to ascertain why it had come about or, at the very least, to address a request to the Venice Commission for clarification. It held that Venice Commission was wrong to consider that a complaint to the Constitutional Court was possible, as the Constitution had explicitly precluded this possibility, providing instead for the right (sic) to file an application with the Court. It also refused to examine whether this restriction was proportionate, declaring itself incompetent given that the limitation was introduced by means of a constitutional amendment, but held that, in any case, the Appeals College (as SAC was referred to at the time) could review appeals against IQC decisions and that assessees could file a complaint with the Court (Annex 1, § 68). Put simply, the Constitutional Court **never** endorsed the limitation of the assessees' right to file a constitutional court complaint; finding that the relevant restriction was introduced by an amendment to the Constitution (precisely in order to, one can reasonably assume, prevent its judicial review; see *Baka v Hungary* [GC], no. 20261/12, § 115, 23 June 2016²⁶). It simply

²⁵ [Law No. 252/2023](#) *On the external evaluation of judges and prosecutors and amendments of some regulatory acts*, Article 19.

²⁶ “115. Nonetheless, the applicant’s access to a court was impeded by the fact that the impugned measure, namely the premature termination of his mandate as President of the Supreme Court, **was included in the transitional provisions of the Organisation and Administration of the Courts Act**, entering into force on 1 January 2012. **This precluded him from contesting that measure before the Service Tribunal, which he would have been able to do in the event of a dismissal on the basis of the existing legal framework [...]**”. It is recalled that, under Article F (3) *in finem* of the Annex to the Constitution, SAC cannot review the constitutionality of the vetting scheme’s principles – another purposefully built-in “safeguard” against the review of the constitutionality of the vetting scheme.

declared itself incompetent and desisted from reviewing the proportionality of the restriction, thus failing to take a stance on a particularly crucial issue.

33. Summarizing the above, Res Publica notes that the selection and appointment processes of the members of the vetting bodies were tainted by numerous shortcomings, chief among which being the Parliament's full discretion in appointing candidates who did not meet the relevant criteria. What is more, these shortcomings are *structural* in nature as they relate to the extremely short time frame available for the review of the candidates' qualifications (which led to the unheard of practice of asking candidates to self-declare if they met some of the criteria) or are embedded in the framework itself (such as the highly politicized method of appointment), shortcomings that cannot but taint the appointment of *all* vetting bodies' members (*Advance Pharma sp. z o.o v. Poland*, op. cit., § 316). Neither the Ombudsperson, nor the IMO nor the Parliament had the time and resources and – in relation to the IMO and Parliament – the willingness of ensuring the conduct of objective and merit-based selection and appointment processes. As a result, the only safeguard against these shortcomings would have been the possibility of challenging the selection and appointment processes before an independent judicial body, with the Venice Commission considering that this role should fall on the proper Constitutional Court. Nevertheless it is now clear that by means of the third draft of the constitutional amendments, Parliament purposefully sought to deprive the proper Constitutional Court of this competence - hence both the elevation of the SAC from a chamber of the High Court to a chamber of the Constitutional Court and the constitutionally entrenched limitation introduced by Article F(3) of the Annex to the Constitution (Annex 1), explicitly precluding SAC from reviewing the compatibility of the main re-evaluation principles with the Constitution (Annex 3, JR 5/2021, § 43) and the Convention.

34. Concluding, and considering that two (to date) out of nine SAC members have been found to have been appointed in blatant violation of the relevant criteria and the structural shortcomings in the selection and appointment processes observed above, it clearly stands to reason that not only were Messrs. L.D. and A.H. unlawfully appointed but also other vetting bodies' members might have also been so appointed (*Wałęsa v. Poland*, no. 50849/21, § 324, 329, 23 November 2023) – indeed, and on the basis of the *Besnik Cani* judgment, it is clear that IQC member A.F.V. was also unlawfully appointed while concerns are also raised by IMO's assistance towards getting SAC member A.S. shortlisted, as it will be seen below. Moreover, it has been established that Ms R.G.S. serves as a SAC member only by means of the exercise of Parliament's totally unreasoned discretion, without meeting the relevant selection criteria and therefore without being appointed "on the basis of merit" (*Xero Flor w Polsce sp. z o.o. v. Poland*, op.cit, § 244).

2. Whether the extraordinary and time-limited nature of the revaluation process can serve as an argument from precluding challenges to the selection and appointment of the members of the revaluation bodies

35. The Court has repeatedly noted the overlapping between the different elements of Article 6; it has thus held the lawful, merit-based appointment of the members of a judicial body is not only important for the latter to qualify as a tribunal for the purposes of Article 6, it is also another guarantee for the personal independence of its members (*Ástráðsson*, op. cit., § 222; *Grzęda v. Poland* [GC], no. 43572/18, § 309, 345, 15 March 2022). It is therefore difficult to see how the extraordinary nature of the re-evaluation process could be used as an argument both to deprive assesses of a series of their rights (such as the right to challenge the

appointment of the vetting bodies' members) but also to legitimize, by invoking the need for judicial certainty, a purposeful violation of Article 6.

36. In *Ástráðsson*, the domestic courts swiftly – thanks to the possibility afforded to unsuccessful candidates to challenge the rejection of their candidacies - established, two weeks before the unlawful appointment of their colleagues took place, that the latter's appointment to the Court of Appeal had been tainted (op. cit., § 284). In the case of the vetting bodies' members, this was not possible because not only did unsuccessful candidates not have a right to judicial review of the decision not to proceed with their appointment, but also because SAC, by virtue of the constitutional amendments, is the only judicial entity in Albania with jurisdiction on all vetting-related issues, and thus was and still finds itself in an open situation of conflict of interest when it comes to reviewing the lawfulness of its members' appointment. In any case, very early on in SAC's mandate, assessees did challenge the method of its members' appointment, to no avail (Annex 3, JR 12/2019, JR 13/2019, JR 2/2020, JR 7/2020). Be that as it may, the Court also disagreed with the Icelandic Supreme Court's assessment that, despite the shortcomings in the appointment, the latter had "become a reality" and should not be upset; the Court noted that the applicant had no interest or even standing to challenge the trial judge's unlawful appointment before his case has heard, noting also that the question whether the impugned judge was to be considered independent or impartial was distinct from the question as to whether his unlawful appointment and sitting on the applicant's panel disqualified it from constituting a tribunal established by law (*Ástráðsson*, op. cit., § 275, 284, 285). Res Publica is aware that the Court also held that with the passage of time, the need for legal certainty might override an applicant's right to tribunal established by law (ibid, § 252); this finding however has to be placed in the context of the factual background of the that case. First, the judge whose appointment to the Court of Appeal was found to be unlawful was an already serving judge, whose original judicial appointment was never put in question. In other words, and unlike the vetting bodies' members, she was a *lawfully appointed judge who was unlawfully promoted* to the Court of Appeal. It is to be noted in this respect that the Court in *Xhoxhaj* has indirectly admitted that the members of SAC have rather limited judicial skills and expertise, at least in vetting / disciplinary proceedings (op. cit., § 333).

37. Second, as noted above, unsuccessful candidates for a position to the Icelandic Court of Appeal had the possibility of challenging the rejection of their candidacies, thus affording domestic courts with the possibility of reviewing the lawfulness of their colleagues' appointment. No such possibility existed in the instant case.

38. Third, defendants in proceedings conducted by the impugned judge in *Ástráðsson* also had a free-standing right to challenge her appointment in front of another court and argue that his Article 6 right to a tribunal established by law was violated – but this is not the case with assessees in the context of the re-evaluation proceedings against them, as they can only challenge the lawfulness of the appointment of SAC members before SAC itself. Such a complaint would clearly have no real prospects of success, given SAC members' evident self-interest in turning down such a complaint - particularly in light of their highly corporatist mentality, as seen in their persistent failure to take any measures in relation to their former colleagues L.D. and A.H. before SPAK indicted them²⁷ and asked for their suspension) but

²⁷ It is clear that all SAC members were aware that at least Mr. L.D. had been unlawfully appointed; if the Court considered that his dismissal had been on public record for the applicant in *Sevdari* and hence she had constructive knowledge of that fact during her vetting proceedings (op. cit., §110), the same would clearly apply to SAC members. Rather, it is highly likely that SAC members *did* in fact know about Mr. L.D.'s unlawful appointment

also because, as SAC has averred, it has no competence to review the lawfulness of (its own) members' appointment, given that this fell within the competence of the Ombudsperson, the IMO and the Parliament.

39. Summarizing, Res Publica recalls its previous point to the effect that the situation obtaining in Albania before the adoption of the vetting legal and regulatory frameworks was different from the one obtaining in Armenia before the amendments that were the object of the application in *Gyulumyan and Others v. Armenia* (op. cit.). In the instant case, the competent authorities were fully aware of the need to retain the possibility for assessees to challenge decisions of the appellate vetting body before the proper Constitutional Court but purposefully amended the relevant provisions in order to prevent the exercise of such a right, a right which was well entrenched in the Albanian legal order: thus the Supreme Court's Joint Benches, in decision no. 2/2011, had held that any shortcoming in the appointment of the members of the trial panel rendered the judgment null and void (Annex 1).

40. Nevertheless, assessees in the re-evaluation proceedings are fully precluded from challenging even the most egregious shortcomings in the appointment of SAC members, even after the delivery of the Court's judgments in *Besnik Cani* and *Sevdari v. Albania*. Thus *post-Besnik Cani*, SAC has in at least seven cases (Annex 3, JR 43/2022, JR 48/2022, JR 3/2023, JR 12/2023, JR 31/2023, JR 38/2023) refused to review challenges of the lawfulness of the appointment of vetting bodies' members, primarily on grounds of administrative expediency, namely that allowing such challenges would bring the vetting to a standstill (see e.g. Annex 3, JR 43/2022, section 14.2.iv). Res Publica also finds particularly interesting SAC's argument that only the impartiality of members of vetting bodies who have lied before the parliamentary commission and have therefore committed a criminal offence can be challenged (Annex 3, JR 3/2023, §10.1.10), in an open act of defiance – and not the only one – of the Court's holdings in *Besnik Cani* to the effect that criminal liability is distinct from an administrative / disciplinary one and that regardless of any criminal liability incurred, not meeting the eligibility criteria in a manifest breach of domestic law that taints the appointment (op. cit., § 94, 96, 99-100).

41. Another reason why SAC's aforementioned statement (to the effect that only the impartiality of members of vetting bodies found guilty in criminal proceedings can be challenged) is interesting is that it stands in stark contrast to SAC's approach in granting requests for exceptional review under Article 494 Civil Procedure Code. SAC has already rejected three such requests regarding SAC decisions rendered by SAC panels in which former SAC member L.D. sat, holding that the final sentencing of a SAC member cannot, under domestic law as applicable in the context of vetting, serve as grounds for reopening the proceedings. Applicants can secure such a reopening only after the conclusion of the proceedings before the Court (Annex 2, § 13.4). In other words, even if it is established that a member of a vetting body has lied before the Parliamentary Commission and has been found guilty in criminal proceedings, an assessee cannot secure the reopening of their proceedings but has to raise this argument before the Court. It is only if the latter specifically indicates in its judgment the reopening of the proceedings will an assessee be afforded redress for the violation of their Article 6 rights – but again, without running into a new set of problems, namely SAC's self-professed inability to form a new panel to review such requests.

but considered, like the IMO, that this did not entail any disciplinary liability. In other words, while it was widely known that he did not meet the appointment criteria, no measures were taken either by the IMO (which in fact considered that no issue arose) or SAC until SPAK, to its credit, indicted him.

3. *Whether SAC's constitutional jurisdiction includes the mandate of reviewing the lawfulness of the appointment of the vetting bodies' members during and post vetting proceedings*

42. Res Publica hardly needs to answer this question, as SAC itself has held that, under Article F(3) of the Annex to the Constitution (Annex 1), it has no such mandate. It would however point out that SAC's stance raises legitimate questions as to whether SAC has full jurisdiction in fact and in law and is therefore a court established by law (see *Beaumartin v. France*, no. 15287/89, § 38, 24 November 1994; *Ramos Nunes de Carvalho e Sá v. Portugal* [GC], nos 55391/13 et seq, § 192, 6 November 2018; *Ovcharenko and Kolos v. Ukraine*, no. 27276/15 and 33692/15, §§ 124-125, 12 January 2023). While admittedly the Court has considered that SAC constitutes a court, it did so in the context of the *Xhoxhaj* case (op. cit. § 333) in which the relevant issues did not arise. Thus in that case the Court was not called to examine whether SAC's self-professed lack of jurisdiction to review the regularity and lawfulness of the appointment of the vetting bodies members, to assess whether the 15 years ban on the appointment to certain posts and positions in the justice system is proportionate (Annex 1, JR 42/2020). Nor did it examine SAC's refusal to reopen the proceedings on the basis of provisions of Article 494 Civil Procedure Code other than letter ë, or the importance of the explicit prohibition of Article F(3) of the Annex to the Constitution on SAC to review the constitutionality of key aspects of the vetting scheme. Res Publica firmly believes that they above limitations on SAC's powers strongly suggest that the SAC does not enjoy full jurisdiction in law and in fact. Res Publica also contends that, when faced with credible allegations of unlawful appointment of two of its members, SAC should have *proprio motu* taken the necessary steps without waiting for SPAK to indict them (see in this respect *Remli v. France*, no. 16839/90, § 48, 23 April 1996; Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) C-542/18 RX-II, C-543/18 RX-1, *Review Simpson and HG v Council and Commission*, 26 March 2020, § 57), which it did not.

43. Res Publica finds particularly interesting SAC's decision JR 12/2024; this is because it concerns a request for reopening on the basis of L.D.'s final conviction and because it was issued post the *Besnik Cani* and *Sevdari* judgments, the holdings of which, Res Publica reiterates, are quite crystalline. Nevertheless in its decision SAC unanimously held among others that under the domestic legislative and regulatory framework, it does not have the competence to reopen proceedings (ibid., §11.14). Moreover, the fact that under the vetting process, it is assesseees who shoulder the burden of proof, effectively means that they (the assesseees) cannot claim to be unaware of facts or arguments that they failed to raise during their re-evaluation proceedings (ibid., § 12.7) [since, effectively, by not raising these arguments then, they have waived their right to do so in the context of reopening proceedings. SAC seems to have "forgotten" that, to those who did challenge the appointment of the vetting bodies' members during their vetting proceedings (e.g. Mr. Besnik Cani) and both before and after the *Besnik Cani* judgment, its answer was that it had no competence to review the vetting bodies members' appointment. With this circular argument (which only established that at no point and in any kind of vetting proceedings (original / reopened) can assesseees challenge the appointment of vetting bodies' members) SAC is indirectly suggesting to assesseees that their only hope for having a case reopened lies with the Court – thus forcing them to spend time and resources in bringing a case before it and unnecessarily burdening the Court with essentially repetitive applications.

44. SAC admits that, in any case, it cannot form a fresh panel to review requests for reopening, characterizing this impossibility not as an “omission” on the part of the legislator but as an expression of its will (ibid, § 12.8) – beholden to Parliament, SAC clearly did not see it fit to consider whether the will of the legislator was compatible with the Constitution and the Convention, showing again the SAC ignores the ratio of the *Ástráðsson* and *Besnik Cani* judgments. As per SAC, the only option available to assessees following the delivery of a final judgment is to file an application with the Court, and it is only on the basis of a Court judgment that they can request the reopening of the proceedings against them (ibid, § 13.2, 13.4, 13.6). Referring to the Court’s “orienting” [sic] judgment in *Sevdari v. Albania* regarding the application of Article 494 Civil Procedure Code, SAC argues that it is not binding on it since SAC has not pronounced itself by means of a decision on the issue (!); it concludes by holding that assessees cannot invoke any of the grounds set out in that Article in order to request the reopening of the proceedings in their case, with the exception of cases where said reopening has been indicated by the Court, in which the request for reopening will be granted on the basis of Article 494(ë) Civil Procedure Code (ibid, § 14.1, 17). SAC is again kicking the can down the road (to Strasbourg): how can applicants, after securing the reopening of their case thanks to the Court judgment, have their case reviewed by a freshly formed SAC panel, given SAC’s own admission, set out only a few paragraphs above, that such a panel cannot be formed? It is very likely that SAC is hinting that, given the delays involved in litigating the case before the Court, the reopening will take place before the proper Constitutional Court (which will take over SAC’s work at the end of its mandate) and so no problem of objective impartiality will arise; if that’s the case, then another legacy of the vetting scheme would be the Constitutional Court’s (and subsequently the Court’s) increased workload.

45. Turning to the parallel opinions in JR12/2034, Res Publica would single out the one delivered by SAC member A.S. who on the one hand found that since there no explicit restrictions SAC could reopen proceedings on any of the grounds set out in Article 494 but, in the interests of judicial consistency, joined the majority in rejecting the request (ibid., § 7). Evidently SAC’s case-law consistency is more important than respecting the Court’s judgments – let alone the assessees’ rights.

46. Were one to sum up SAC decision JR 12/2024, the following would be a pretty accurate summary: a chamber of the Constitutional Court, whose members have not taken the oath of the Constitutional Court judge as it will be seen below, holds that it has no jurisdiction, under a legal provision pertaining to the Supreme Court, to reopen a case unless it is so indicated to it by the Court, leaving unaddressed the issue how the fresh panel would be formed.

4. Whether SAC’s refusal to abide by the Court’s clear holdings in Besnik Cani and Sevdari constitutes a threat to the Court’s functioning

47. As noted above, SAC continues to refuse to review the appointment of its members in the context of original vetting proceedings. Turning to reviewing the same issue in the context of reopened proceedings, while SAC has not ruled out the possibility, it has limited such reopening only in cases where an assessee secures an injunction to that effect by the Court – without, it needs repeating, elaborating how a fresh panel untainted by lack of objective impartiality will be formed. This in turn however means that SAC and the drafters of the justice reform have unilaterally designated the Court as a court of third instance – giving new meaning

to Article F(8) of the Annex to the Constitution²⁸-, not only putting SAC's very nature as a tribunal in question (due to its limited competence to reopen proceedings) but also risking undermining the Court's functioning, as SAC effectively obliges assesses to apply to the Court (see by analogy, *Camara c. Belgique*, no. 49255/22, § 121, 145, 18 July 2023; that case concerned domestic failures to abide by domestic court judgments, yet Res Publica considers that the same principle applies in the present case regarding the Court's *Sevdari* and *Besnik Cani* judgments). Res Publica also considers that this persistent purposeful misrepresentation – indeed, outright rejection- of the Court's abundantly clear holdings in the aforementioned judgments constitutes a particular affront towards the Court, one that amounts itself to a violation of Article 6 (see, by analogy, *Serrano Contreras v. Spain (no. 2)*, no. 2236/19, §§ 37-39, 26 October 2021) and puts into question the assumption that SAC is willing to execute the two judgments in good faith (*Aydin Sefa Akay v. Türkiye*, no. 59/17, §150, 23 April 2024, request for referral pending; *Repeşco et Repeşcu c. République de Moldova*, no. 39272/15, § 30, 3 October 2023).²⁹ In fact, and echoing Judge Kūris's partly dissenting opinion in *Turan and Others v. Turkey*, given SAC's persistent and wholly unreasoned refusal to abide by the Court's clear and unambiguous holdings in *Sevdari* and *Besnik Cani* whether in original or reopened vetting proceedings, one might even form the impression that SAC is *at the very least not overly concerned* as to what impact its approach will have on the Court's high workload and limited resources, if not diverting its caseload to it on purpose (no. 75805/16 and 426 others, § 38, 23 November 2021). It is also of some interest that in so doing, SAC is *also* defying the Albanian Government (which argued before the Court that proceedings could be reopened; SAC should have paid more attention to the responsibility Albania might incur by not taking into consideration the Albanian Government's assertion before the Court (see *Willems et Gorjon c. Belgique*, nos. 74209/16 and 3 others, § 51, 66, 21 September 2021) – unless, of course, SAC suggests that the Albanian Government's contention before the Court as to the possibility of reopening the proceedings was ill-founded – if only because of the impossibility of forming a fresh panel, untainted by lack of objective impartiality. It is also defying the Constitutional Court, which in rejected assesses' complaints against SAC decisions, has consistently held that SAC should ensure full respect of their rights (*Besnik Cani*, op. cit., §§ 41-43).

48. Res Publica recalls that the Court has been critical of arguments adduced by domestic courts to the effect that provisions in national constitutions prevent them from ensuring compliance with the Convention (*Grzęda v. Poland*, op. cit., § 340). It is of a certain interest that the respondent state in that case used that argument in order to shield its judicial reform from criticism. The Court has also been critical of domestic courts – particularly the highest ones- which: “exclude the operation and application of the Convention provisions by, as the Government seem to suggest in the present case, “removing” them, together with the Court's final and binding judgments, from the legal system” (*Wałęsa v. Poland*, op.cit., § 144).

²⁸ The article provides as follows: “Assessee may exercise the right of appeal to the European Court of Human Rights.” Res Publica considered that the inclusion of this rather odd provision meant to serve as an acknowledgement that the respondent Government would not raise any pleas as to the inapplicability of Article 6 in re-evaluation proceedings. Quite apart from the fact that questions regarding the applicability of Article 6 relate to the Court's competence *rationae materiae* and are to be examined of its own motion (*Pasquinelli and Others v. San Marino*, no. 24622/22, § 68, 29 August 2024, not final) so the Court hardly needed such a “concession” by Albanian law, it would be interesting to see what will happen if an assessee decides to challenge their dismissal before the United Nations Human Rights Committee.

²⁹ Regarding a similar approach in the context of Article 11, with the Court referring to its holdings on the same issue in the context of a previous judgment, see *Maison de la Civilisation macédonienne et autres c. Grèce*, no. 1295/10, §§ 37- 44, 9 July 2015)

49. Moreover, by shielding itself behind Article F(3) of the Annex to the Constitution, SAC seems not only to challenge the primacy of the Convention but also to be acting in violation of Article 122 of the Constitution regarding the force of international agreements in the Albanian domestic legal order, thus failing to respect, at one stroke, **both** the Convention **and** the Constitution – a truly remarkable feat for a body set up to promote the rule of law. This is all the more so since in JR 12/2024, SAC member A.S., in her parallel opinion, acknowledges that the Court clearly indicated that a reopening of the proceedings can be premised on any of the cases set out in Article 494 Civil Procedure Code and that there is no *explicit* restriction on SAC from reopening a case under any of them– yet in open defiance of the Court’s holdings, agreed with the majority that proceedings cannot be reopened unless so indicated by the Court (Annex 2, § 6). One can compare this to the Polish Supreme Court’s exhortation to Polish judges to give precedence to European Union law over domestic law regarding the unlawful appointment of judges (*Advance Pharma sp. z o.o v. Poland*, op. cit., §142 *in finem*).

III. Applying the Court / CJEU tests regarding the appointment of judges to the appointment of members of the vetting bodies

50. As Res Publica has argued at length above, SAC has never applied in practice the *Ástráðsson* three-tiered test in relation to assesses’ claims over the unlawful appointment of the vetting bodies’ members. Similarly, while the Court applied it in the context of the *Besnik Cani* case regarding former SAC member L.D., it based itself on contextual findings from the criminal proceedings against the latter, as no proceedings regarding specifically the lawfulness of his appointment took place domestically. Moreover, while referring to the CJEU test set out in the *A.K.* case in *Xhoxhaj* (op. cit, §§ 225 – 229), the Court did not apply it to the facts of the case, given its decision to not review the appointment of the vetting bodies’ members in general (op. cit, § 296). It is therefore instructive to examine whether, apart from any individual responsibility vetting bodies’ members might incur, the very method of their appointment – and in particular, the way it was implemented – would pass the relevant tests developed by the Court and the CJEU.

1. Applying the Ástráðsson three-tiered test in the context of the appointment of the vetting bodies’ members in light of the shortcomings identified above

51. Regarding the first criterion, namely whether there was a manifest breach of the domestic law, Res Publica considers that it should be answered in the affirmative, in light of the Court’s holding that the: “eligibility requirements for the appointment of judges constitute fundamental rule whose breach undermines the effect of the “established by law” requirement” (*Besnik Cani*, op. cit., §99). As argued above, and as both the Ombudsperson and the IMO have explicitly acknowledged, neither of them had the time or resources to carry out an in-depth review of the candidates’ application files. Moreover, it is clear that the vetting legal and regulatory frameworks were the result of political negotiations between the two major political parties, and given the lack of a ranking system, Parliament had unfettered discretion to appoint any candidate from “List A” without having to provide even a rudimentary reasoning as to its choice, after holding a 5-minute interview of each candidate. The procedure of appointment of the vetting bodies’ members was a far cry from the previous one which, while also problematic, did at least offer some checks and balances. Res Publica recalls that the CJEU articulated and applied the non-regression principle in the field of appointment of judges, suggesting that such standards cannot, once adopted, be lowered (CJEU C-896/19, *Repubblika v Prime Minister of Malta*, 20 April 2021, §§ 63-64). It is noted in this respect that SAC members have the same

status as Constitutional Court judges and the relevant law is applicable to them; this however also means that they should have taken an oath before the President of the Republic, as required under Article 129 of the Constitution (Annex 1). Moreover, the importance attached in the Albanian legal order on the obligation of a judge to take an oath before their appointment can be seen by the fact that Article 38 Law 96/2016 *On the Status of Judges and Prosecutors in the Republic of Albania* specifically provides for the retention of the act of oath in the judge's personal file (Annex 1). It is also recalled that according to the Venice Commission's interpretation of Article 129, "taking an oath in front of the President is a precondition for taking up office".³⁰ The fact that no constitutional provision explicitly provides an exemption for SAC members from this obligation strongly suggests that they should, *qua* Constitutional Court judges, have taken the relevant oath which as noted above is a constituent element of their judicial mandate. While Res Publica cannot divine the reasons behind the lack of an explicit provision regarding the issue of the oath of the SAC members, it would attribute this oversight to the hasty adoption of the vetting scheme. It is recalled that up until the penultimate draft of the Vetting scheme, SAC would be a chamber of the High Court and its decisions amenable, at least on some grounds, to challenge before the Constitutional Court— indeed the Venice Commission explicitly called for this possibility. There was thus no reason for the SAC members to take an oath since their decisions would be reviewed by a proper court. It appears therefore that when the SAC was "upgraded" to a Constitutional Court chamber – almost certainly in order to ensure that its decisions would not be amenable to judicial review on any grounds- the issue of the oath was quite simply overlooked; it would not have been difficult for the SAC members to have taken the oath. To that end, SAC's reasoning that while the elevation of SAC to a Constitutional Court chamber was meant to serve as a further safeguard of its members' independence but that at the same time, the non-taking of the oath by (without there being an specific exception foreseen for) SAC members does not affect its integrity as a Constitutional Court chamber, seems contradictory at best and an desperate attempt to whitewash a glaring omission at worst (Annex 3, JR 3/2023, § 10.1.2).

52. The above shortcomings clearly give rise to as a systemic problem affecting the integrity of the appointment process of **all** vetting bodies' members and particularly those of the SAC (*Wałęsa v. Poland*, no. 50849/21, § 324, 23 November 2023), regardless of any additional (and personal) disciplinary and criminal liability they might incur for their acts or omissions during the selection and appointment processes. Res Publica notes that even if it were to be held that the selection and appointment processes fully complied with domestic legislation, it would still remain to be assessed whether they could be considered: "lawful for the purposes of the Convention, notably whether the relevant legal framework was foreseeable in its application and compatible with the rule of law and whether the decision-making process, seen as a whole, provided the applicant with the requisite safeguards against arbitrariness" (*Wałęsa v. Poland*, op. cit., § 289; see also *Reczkowicz v. Poland*, op. cit., § 222). Res Publica recalls in this connection that the Convention forms an integral part of the Albanian legal order and is directly applicable (*ALBA GAMES and Eduard Biti v. Albania* (dec), no. 47108/08, §§ 23-24, 11 April

³⁰ Venice Commission, *Opinion on the appointment of judges to the Constitutional Court*, [CDL-AD\(2020\)010](#), 19 June 2020, paragraphs 99-100. Res Publica notes that in request for reopening no 110-24/2022 (JR), filed on 09 August 2023, the assessee asked for the reopening of the proceedings in his case due to the failure of SAC members, *qua* Constitutional Court members to take the oath prescribed by Article 129 of the Constitution. He has also asked the SAC to refer the issue either to the Court, to the Venice Commission, or to the Constitutional Court. To date, no hearing date has been set. One of the authors of the current submission has contributed to the drafting of that request for reopening.

2024). Even if a domestic piece of legislation is considered to be constitutional, this does not *ipso facto* mean that it complies with the Convention.

53. Turning to the second criterion, namely as to whether the breach of domestic law pertained to a fundamental rule of the procedure for appointing judges, Res Publica considers, as also held by the Court in *Besnik Cani* (op. cit., § 99) that the answer is again affirmative. The problem lies in fact not so much in the relevant provisions themselves (deficient as they might be) but in the fact that they were **never implemented** as the competent authorities (Ombudsperson, IMO, Parliament) either did not have the time or the resources or the willingness to observe them. It cannot be that candidates for the highest judicial posts in Albania during the last 34 years, with disciplinary power over vetted Constitutional Court judges, were to be appointed on the basis of, inter alia, a self-declaration that they had not incurred disciplinary liability. It cannot be that Parliament, without any reasoning (presumably because, one suspects, there was no such reasoning), proceeded to appoint Ms R.G.S. even though she was found **twice** by both the Ombudsperson and the IMO, not to meet the selection criteria and even though there were also other candidates from “List A” available. It cannot be that for years, the authorities could not ascertain whether former SAC members L.D. and A.D. (or two out of nine SAC members – a 22% failure rate) were unlawfully appointed, and that only after criminal complaints filed by assesseses and SPAK’s actions was their mandate terminated – with their SAC colleagues almost certainly (at least regarding Mr. L.D.) being aware of their unlawful appointment. And it cannot also be that IQC member A.F.V. ironically also an expert engaged in the context of the justice reform), who finds herself in exactly the same position as former SAC member L.D., continues to serve (see below, § 61).

53. Turning to the third criterion, namely whether the allegations regarding the “right to a tribunal established by law” were effectively reviewed and remedied by the domestic courts, the answer is clearly in the negative. As presented above, SAC both before and after the Court’s judgments in *Besnik Cani* and *Sevdari* but also in the context of both ordinary and reopened re-evaluation proceedings has refused to review claims regarding any shortcoming in the appointment of the vetting bodies’ members.

2. Applying the Reczkowicz variant of the Ástráðsson three-tiered test in the context of the appointment of the vetting bodies’ members in light of the shortcomings identified above

54. The Court applied the *Ástráðsson* three-tiered test in the context of the Polish justice reform in the case of *Reczkowicz v. Poland*. More specifically, the case concerned the grave irregularities in appointment of judges to the newly established Supreme Court’s Disciplinary Chamber, which also heard disciplinary cases against lawyers, and the Court was called to review whether the hearing of the applicant’s case before it gave rise to a violation of her right to a tribunal established by law, given the numerous irregularities in the appointment of its members. Turning to the first criterion, and while the Court acknowledged that the reasons behind the new method of appointment of the Chamber’s judges could be seen as legitimate, these were just one factor to be taken into consideration in the overall balancing exercise (op.cit., § 237). The Court found that that new appointment process, whereby the judges – members of the National Council for the Judiciary (who in turn appointed the members of the Supreme Court’s Disciplinary Chamber) were appointed by the Parliament (and not, any more, by their peers), undermined the Council’s independence vis-à-vis the executive and legislative powers and was in violation of domestic law (op. cit., § 264). Regarding the second criterion, the Court held that the breach of domestic legislation allowed the executive and the legislature

to interfere directly or indirectly in the appointment of judges and was thus of a particular gravity (op. cit., §274, 277). Turning to the third criterion, the Court took into account the respondent Government's acknowledgement that no relevant domestic remedies were available (op.cit., §§ 278-279).

55. Applying the aforementioned principles regarding the selection and appointment of the vetting bodies' members, Res Publica notes the following: **first**, and regardless whether the adoption of the vetting scheme was necessary in order to address corruption in the Albanian judiciary, it (the vetting scheme) conferred unfettered discretion on Parliament in appointing the members of the vetting bodies, discretion that it hardly enjoyed under the previous appointment procedure. In fact, while in *Reczkowicz* the Court found problematic the fact that the Government could indirectly (after tampering with the composition of National Council for the Judiciary) elect judges, in the case of Albania the Parliament, after a **political agreement** was reached for the appointment of the vetting bodies' members, was **explicitly** vested with the power to appoint the vetting bodies' members who were not judges *directly*, without being limited by any ranking order, and also had the power to bypass the recommendations of the independent authorities in appointing them. **Second**, Parliament clearly took advantage of this discretion; it paid no attention to the fact that e.g. former SAC member L.D. and incumbent IQC member A.F.V. mentioned during the interviews before the ad hoc Parliamentary Commissions that they had served as judges but failed to mention that they were dismissed. Moreover, Parliament not only appointed substitute IQC member P.S. – even though he proudly admitted before the ad hoc Parliamentary Commission that he did not meet an eligibility criterion. Parliament also moved SAC member R.G.S. from “List B” to “List A” and appointed her. **Third**, as seen above in the context of the *Ástráðsson* three-tiered test, neither unsuccessful candidates nor assesses have a right to challenge the appointment of SAC members before SAC – even if such a challenge were to be held to be an effective one, despite the SAC members' obvious lack of impartiality.

3. Applying the Court of Justice of the European Union three-tiered test in the context of the appointment of the vetting bodies' members in light of the shortcomings identified above

56. In addition to failing to pass the *Ástráðsson* three-tiered test, both in its original form and the *Reczkowicz* variant, Res Publica contends that SAC would also fail to pass a similar three-pronged test set out by the CJEU in order to assess whether the then newly established Disciplinary Chamber of the Polish Supreme Court qualified as a “tribunal established by law”. In its C 585/18, C 624/18 and C 625/18, *A.K. and others Independence of the Disciplinary Chamber of the Supreme Court*, 19 November 2019 judgment the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), after referring to the Court's case-law, held that a court cannot be considered as an independent and impartial tribunal “[...] where the objective circumstances in which that court was formed, its characteristics and the means by which its members have been appointed are capable of giving rise to legitimate doubts, in the minds of subjects of the law, as to the imperviousness of that court to external factors, in particular, as to the direct or indirect influence of the legislature and the executive and its neutrality with respect to the interests before it and, thus, may lead to that court not being seen to be independent or impartial with the consequence of prejudicing the trust which justice in a democratic society must inspire in subjects of the law.” (op. cit., §166). The CJEU also held that *any* national court reviewing a case falling within its jurisdiction, has the “obligation to disapply any provision of national law which is contrary to a provision of EU law with direct effect in the case pending before it” (op. cit., §161). Moreover, the CJEU also held that in cases where there were concerns about

the independence and impartiality of a court which has exclusive jurisdiction in a particular case, then another court regarding which no such concerns have been raised has the obligation to hear that case (op. cit., §166). The three elements that the CJEU indicated should be taken into consideration when assessing the impartiality and independence of a tribunal were the following: first, whether the court whose independence and impartiality are in question has been granted exclusive jurisdiction on a particular matter, by virtue of a contentious legislative amendment (op. cit., § 147); second, whether the impugned court consists solely of newly appointed judges (op. cit., § 150) and third, whether the impugned court, in contrast to other courts, enjoys a particularly high degree of autonomy within the referring court (in this case, the Polish Supreme Court) (op. cit., §151). While the CJEU considered that none of these factors could, on their own, warrant questioning the independence and impartiality of the impugned court in question, taken together they could constitute a sufficient legal basis for finding that the impugned court was neither independent nor impartial (op. cit., §152).

57. Attempting an application of the afore-mentioned three-pronged test to SAC, Res Publica notes the following. **First**, the SAC has been granted exclusive and final jurisdiction in the re-evaluation process, as well as the disciplinary process of both serving judges and SAC members. Moreover, the establishment of the SAC was made possible only following the McAllister plus agreement, under the terms of which the two main political parties *had* to consent to the speedy establishment of the vetting bodies. It was none other than OSCE/ODIHR that was critical of the McAllister plus agreement and its impact on the June 2017 Parliamentary Elections. The political parties were also granted unfettered discretion in both selecting and appointing the vetting bodies' members. **Second**, the composition of the SAC consists in its entirety of newly appointed judicial officials, the vast majority of whom were not judges in the past and who, as noted above, have been granted wide-ranging competences. **Third**, the SAC is largely an independent court and only nominally a chamber of the Constitutional Court – indeed, it is a “Constitutional Court” *within* the Constitutional Court.

IV. The role of the International Monitoring Operation in the vetting scheme: ensuring the vetting scheme's “success” – at any cost

58. While aware that, regardless of any blame to be ascribed to its international partners, it is the respondent Government that bears responsibility under the Convention (*Capital Bank AD v. Bulgaria*, no. 49429/99, § 111, 24 November 2005), Res Publica considers it important to assess the stance of the International Monitoring Operation (IMO) Observers, given both their involvement in the selection of the shortlisted candidates for the vetting bodies to be presented to Parliament and their competence, under Article 17 Vetting Act (Annex 1), to request the launching of disciplinary measures against vetting bodies' members.

59. Regarding their role in the selection and shortlisting in “List A” of the candidates for vetting bodies, the IMO acknowledged that it did not have enough time to carry out a proper vetting (the term is used advisedly) of the 193 candidates' skills and qualifications – the time allocated was less than two weeks³¹, which was clearly not adequate, leading to the possibility that at

³¹ European Commission European External Action Service (EEAS), [Most frequently asked questions on the International Monitoring Operation \(IMO\)](#) : “How is it possible that the IMO did not spot these matters of which Mr Daci is accused? The IMO was part of the pre-vetting.

• The Vetting Law and the Albanian Constitution attributes a specific monitoring role to the IMO in the process before the formation of the vetting institutions. The IMO Observers utilised the period of less than two weeks

least some of the vetting bodies' members who were appointed did not meet the selection criteria – indeed, as noted above, two (to date) SAC members have been found to have been appointed irregularly. Given the importance (and presumably one-off nature) of the vetting in Albania, it could have been expected of the highly knowledgeable IMO Observers to have raised their concerns about the limited time at their disposal and asked for an extension; after all, dissatisfied with the limited number of candidates in the first call for proposals, Parliament and the Albanian Government's international partners had agreed to re-issue the call for candidates. Granting at the minimum a full month's time to the IMO to carry out an in-depth review of the candidates' files would have caused no perceptible delay in the vetting but would have helped ensure its integrity, which was presumably what the presence of the IMO was intended to do.

60. Perhaps more importantly however, the IMO Observers can hardly claim to have been impartial and objective during those two weeks. Thus while in their Final Recommendation submitted to the Ombudsperson on 7 April 2017 the IMO Observers “opted to recommend the exclusion from possible appointment to the vetting bodies of candidates characterised by real or apparent conflicts of interest”, in the same document, and while acknowledging that the inclusion of Ms. A.S. (ultimately appointed as a SAC member), given her position, would undermine the public's confidence in justice reform, it proceeded to recommend that she either resign or delegate her duties (Annex 5), with Ms. A.S. opting for the latter. In other words, the independent authority tasked with reviewing the candidates' files, *actively assisted* one candidate in not having her candidacy rejected.³² Res Publica can only speculate as to why the IMO did not make any similar recommendations regarding other candidates, something that would, after all, increase the pool of eligible candidates, since surely other candidates who were considered as having apparent conflicts of interest could have taken, upon the IMO's advice, measures to address them and thus also qualify for inclusion in “List A”. Rather interestingly, and intriguingly, this is not the first time Ms. A.S. (or, rather more accurately, the appointing authorities) finds herself under criticism. In 2014 – not that long before the vetting was launched- , even though she still held the same position in the administration (Secretary General of the Parliament), Ms A.S. was appointed, on the then and currently ruling party's recommendation, as a member to then High Council for Justice; Transparency International was critical of her appointment, considering it to be in violation of *CCJE Opinion No. 10 On the Council for the Judiciary in the service of society*, paragraph 23 of which provides that various categories of officials, among which members of the administration, should not be appointed as members of judicial councils.³³ While it is not up to Res Publica to pass judgment on Ms. A.S.' legal skills, the Parliament's and IMO's insistence to appoint her at the High Council for Justice *pre-vetting* and at SAC for the vetting, is rather surprising; there surely were other equally qualified candidates available.

61. Regarding the IMO's competence in disciplinary proceedings against vetting bodies' members, Res Publica recalls that the IMO refused to request the launching of disciplinary proceedings in the case of L.D., arguing that the irregular appointment was not one of the disciplinary offences listed in Article 16 of the Vetting Act (Annex 6). Even after the *Besnik*

provided to them by law to review all the documentation submitted by candidates and then issued their reasoned assessment and recommendations (as per art. 7 para. 7 of Law 84/2016)[...].”

³² Admittedly though, even if she had been placed in “List B”, Parliament could still – and, with the benefit of hindsight- would have appointed her.

³³ Transparency International, [National Integrity System Assessment Albania 2016](#), 8 September 2016, page 66. See also Bangalore Principles, *op. cit.*, paragraph 96.

Cani judgment and when asked as to what measures it would undertake after being informed that IQC member A.F.V. found herself in the exact same situation as former SAC member L.D. (she was dismissed as a judge in 1997, something that she failed to mention during her interview, during which she did mention that she served as a judge – precisely like former SAC member L.D.), the IMO again responded that being irregularly appointed is not a disciplinary offence and merely “took note” [sic] of the Court’s judgment in *Besnik Cani* (Annex 7); as of the date of writing, there is no information as to whether the IMO will take any measures regarding this issue; those assesseees who challenged her appointment before SAC will now have to wait for the Court to issue a judgment similar to the *Besnik Cani* one, so they can then request before SAC the reopening of the proceedings, in a time and resources-consuming judicial merry-go-round.

62. On a wider note, one could very well form the opinion that the IMO is more concerned with ensuring the “successful” implementation of the re-evaluation process rather than ensuring that the rights of the assesseees are respected: this much was admitted by IMO Observer T.J. at an interview to a Belgian periodical, who stated that the members of the evaluation bodies work with great dedication and “if they do not find anything about a particular judge, they even worry they might have missed something” (Annex 8) – an acknowledgement that assesseees are facing vetting bodies which are prejudiced against them.³⁴ There can therefore be no reason other than the self-serving one of protecting the IMO’s tarnished reputation, why the same IMO Observer would assault SPAK for launching an investigation into former SAC member L.D. and ordering the suspension of his mandate (Annex 9), effectively doing what the IMO should have done (namely carry out an in-depth review of the candidates’ files) but did not do – much like it did not do in the case of former SAC member A.H.. And while it is true that the IMO distanced itself from his statements,³⁵ the fact that, while aware that IQC commissioner A.F.V. was unlawfully appointed, it has not yet taken any steps to launch a disciplinary investigation, nor uttered a word of concern over the open and *repeated* attempts by IQC and Public Commissioners (PC) members to use their incumbent position in order to request from the Government their permanent appointment as judges (going as far as drafting relevant documents and submitting them to the competent state authorities) – even though this is not foreseen by law, unlike the situation with SAC members- (Annex 10; regarding the impact that such negotiations might have on perceptions regarding judicial officials’ impartiality see *Sacilor-Lormines v. France*, no. 65411/01, § 69, 9 November 2006³⁶). On the other hand, the IMO has been vociferously critical of Mr. Besnik Cani’s attempt to secure his reinstatement by applying to the High Prosecutorial Council, invoking the Court’s judgment to that effect (Annex 11) – which it ignored in the case of IQC member A.F.V.- Be that as it may, Res Publica recalls that as seen above, SAC finds itself in a clear situation of conflict of interest in reviewing requests for reopening of proceedings; it has admitted that it cannot form a fresh panel to review such case and that this impossibility was not an oversight but was purposeful (Annex 2, §12.8). In other words, the IMO is calling upon Mr. B.C. to waive his right to a fair trial before an impartial tribunal. In the interest of objectivity, it should be noted that IMO Observer T.J. heavily criticised a SAC decision, bluntly stating that SAC twisted the facts of

³⁴ On the evidentiary value of statements by high-ranking officials see by analogy, *El Masri v. the Former Republic of Macedonia*, no. 39630/09, §163, 13 December 2012.

³⁵ Exit.al, [International Monitoring Operation Distances Itself from Theo Jacobs](#), 31 July 2020.

³⁶ See also United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, [Commentary on the Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct](#), September 2007, paragraphs 91, 145

the case³⁷ in order to confirm an assessee (Annex 12) – a particularly serious allegation- before rather self-conceitedly concluding that “the Albanian citizens” (whose they are presumably the true defenders and guardians) deserved more and better. It is not Res Publica’s role to pass judgment on either SAC’s reasoning or the well-foundedness of the IMO Observer’s allegations. It will merely note that, if he truly considered that the SAC panel had unduly favored the assessee, then he could have requested the launching of disciplinary proceedings against the members of the panel, all the more since Article 16(12) Vetting Act seems to be applicable.³⁸ The fact that, to Res Publica’s best knowledge, no measures were taken suggests that the outburst was merely a flash in a pan with nothing perceptible coming out of it, except from wantonly slandering – with impunity, due to their status- a judge confirmed in duty by SAC.

63. Perhaps however the most conclusive evidence that the IMO was and is exclusively concerned with ensuring, at any cost to the rights of the assessee, the “successful” conclusion of the re-evaluation process, is its stance on the issue of the by now infamous IQC staff retreat / strategy meeting. It was revealed that this 2021 retreat was financed by a well-known Albanian magnate (Annex 13³⁹). As if this were not problematic enough, it transpires that it was the President of the IQC who *solicited* from the insurance company belonging to the Albanian magnate (whose insurance company had already secured a contract to insure the IQC members) to finance that staff retreat. Upon learning this, the IMO addressed a rather sternly worded letter to the IQC – a letter that was not made public and a copy of which was secured following a request for access to documents filed with the European Commission. In its letter, a redacted copy of which was secured by Res Publica, the IMO notes that this “sponsorship agreement” has “important legal and practical implications”, “is harmful to the credibility and reputation of the IQC”, that it is “highly inappropriate for a vetting institution to solicit donations from private entities” and cautions the IQC that similar agreements should not be entered into, while IQC members are asked to consult the IMO in similar cases in the future (Annex 14⁴⁰). It would be condescending towards the Committee of Ministers for Res Publica to set out how problematic is both the fact that the IQC, it bears repeating, *solicited* a donation and that the IMO, while publicly expressing its concern about Mr. Besnik Cani’s filing of an application with the High Prosecutorial Council asking for his reinstatement, did so privately regarding this case – that implicates *all IQC members* (as they cannot but have had constructive knowledge of the sponsor of the event since they attended it) and merely called upon the IQC to not do it again, or whether the IMO and the IQC have the moral wherewithal to pass judgment on the assessee’s moral integrity, who are among others being assessed on whether, for example, they directly or indirectly used their position to obtain a preferential price for an apartment. Instead, Res Publica will confine itself to noting that the issue of whether IQC members have incurred disciplinary liability for, it bears repeating, *soliciting* donations has been drawn to the IMO’s attention, which has also been asked if it would take any disciplinary measures (given that the soliciting of a donation at least seems to constitute a disciplinary

³⁷ The exact phrase has as follows: “Justice is served when a decision is based on facts, not when the facts are adjusted to the desired outcome”.

³⁸ The article provides as follows: “The member of the re-evaluation institution shall be disciplinarily liable, specifically due to: [...] 12. Distorted submission of facts on the acts being issued;”

³⁹ The same article is available in English at Alfapress news portal, [The “secret” sponsor of KPK is Shefqet Kastrati’s insurance company](#), 19 July 2024.

⁴⁰ Res Publica has challenged the necessity for the redaction of the paragraph on the second page of the document and undertakes to notify the Committee of Ministers of any related development.

offence under Art 16(15) Vetting Act.⁴¹ IMO responded by repeating that while harmful to the credibility and reputation of IQC, it did not consider that the “receipt of a donation” gave rise to a disciplinary offence; the response is rather disingenuous, as the main problem was the *soliciting* of the donation, as mentioned in the IMO’s letter to IQC which read that: “It appears, in fact, highly inappropriate for a vetting institution to *solicit* [emphasis added] donations from private entities”) (Annex 15); one wonders if IMO demonstrates the same magnanimity in relation to assesses during their vetting.

64. As if the above were not enough, neither the IMO nor the IQC appear to have considered a rather apparent case of conflict of interest related to the disclosure of this agreement between the IQC and the insurance company. The news story regarding the sponsored retreat broke by a journalist working for the news portal Reporter.al, who filed a request for a copy of that agreement with the IQC; he subsequently challenged the IQC’s refusal before the Right to Information and Data Protection Commissioner, who held that the agreement should be disclosed in its entirety. The IQC challenged the Commissioner’s decision before the First Instance Administrative Court, sitting on a single-member formation, with judge N.H. The latter, by means of judgment 2248, dated 13 September 2022, granted IQC’s request and held that the agreement should not be disclosed.⁴² It was only following an appeal by the Commissioner, with the journalist joining the proceedings as an interested third party, that the Administrative Appeals Court held, on the basis also of the reasoning set out at the beginning of this submission, that the agreement should be disclosed in full (the decision was subsequently challenged by the IQC but eventually upheld by the Supreme Court – in all, more than 30 months after the retreat). What is particularly interesting for present purposes is that judge N.H. was, at the time when she rendered her decision granting IQC’s request to quash the Commissioner’s decision, undergoing vetting before the IQC; the latter, by decision no. 654 dated 28 April 2023, confirmed her in office. Since the Public Commissioner did not file an appeal, nor did the IMO recommend the filing of it, the IQC’s decision is final. Put simply, judge N.H. was called upon to decide upon an important case regarding IQC’s credibility during the time her case was pending before it; during the proceedings, not only did she not request her recusal, but neither the IQC nor the IMO held the fact that she did not do so against her, as they have in much less egregious cases of other assesses. This in turn could mean either that they did not perceive this situation as giving rise to a potential case of conflict of interest – or, at least, of quite apparent lack of objective impartiality – or that for whatever reasons, they closed their eyes to this situation.

65. Given the magnitude and importance of the vetting scheme, it would have been expected that Albania’s international partners that nominated the IMO Observers would have carried out a review of their work and activities, if only in order to identify any shortcomings and address them. On the basis of the European Commission’s answer to a request for access to documents however, it appears that no such evaluation has been carried out (Annex 16).

⁴¹ The article, reproduced also in Annex 1, provides as follows: “The member of the re-evaluation institution shall be disciplinarily liable, specifically due to [...] 15. Unfair direct or indirect benefit of gifts, favours, promises or preferential treatments of any kind, either by lawful actions, granted due to the function he or she exercises or as a result of his or her use of the position;”

⁴² As an aside, one of the grounds invoked by the first instance court to uphold IQC’s request was that, as held by the Court in the *Xhoxhaj v. Albania* judgment, the IQC constituted an independent tribunal established by law under Article 6. Res Publica considers this yet another example of how the Court’s judgments are interpreted at will by domestic courts.

66. Last, in the interests of fairness, Res Publica would like to note that it is not only the IMO that seems to be overly protective of the vetting scheme; Res Publica was rather concerned by its finding that in their report *On the honouring of obligations and commitments by Albania* report, the rapporteurs recommend the closing of the monitoring procedure in respect of Albania. They paint a particularly positive picture of vetting, considering the vetting “a success” and invoking the high number of judges and prosecutors who were dismissed as an argument in favor of the vetting. Rather curiously, however, when referring to vetting-related judgments before the Court, the report contains no reference to the *Besnik Cani* and *Sevdari* judgments or their implications (particularly the *Besnik Cani* one; it is not, after all, an everyday occurrence that an usurper judge is elected as a member of the highest court of a country specifically tasked with rooting out corruption), thought they do refer to the *Thanza* judgment adopted after those two.⁴³ Again, Res Publica will not speculate on the reasons behind this “omission”, though it will reiterate its concern about the rather widespread tendency to “shield” vetting from criticism – to the expense of assessee’s rights. In the interests of fairness, the report is critical of Albania’s failure to satisfactorily address 19 out of 24 GRECO recommendations (including one regarding the Prime Minister’s accountability to the Ministerial Code of Ethics) as well as Albania’s less-than-stellar record in executing Court judgments⁴⁴ - both issues, Res Publica contends, that have an indirect bearing on how the vetting scheme was conceived and implemented.

V. Albania’s unique vetting scheme: a comparative perspective

67. Albania is hardly the only post-communist country facing extensive rule of law issues. It is therefore interesting to examine how Albania’s international partners and other stakeholders have approached the issue of widespread corruption in those countries. Starting with **Armenia**, it was none other than the Venice Commission and the Directorate of Human Rights that cautioned against a wide-ranging (“headstrong”, according to the joint opinion) vetting scheme – indeed, they congratulated the Armenian Government for its back-tracking from such an initiative and adopting more tailor-made solutions.⁴⁵ Regarding **Bosnia-Herzegovina**, a report drawn up by a group of experts headed by Mr. Priebe, while painting an image similar to Albania in terms of low levels of efficiency of the justice system, failure to address high-level corruption, serious allegations of corruption in the appointment of the head of the High Judicial and Prosecutorial Councils which were never investigated, the failure to make use of the existing integrity mechanisms for judges, ineffective judicial training programs funded by the EU,⁴⁶ recommended against the holding of vetting of judges.⁴⁷ It is recalled that the same expert group had recommended against the holding of a vetting process in **North Macedonia**; the

⁴³ Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe (PACE), [doc 15940](#), 26 March 2024, paragraphs 10, 71, 91. By means of [Resolution 2544\(2024\)](#), dated 17 April 2024, PACE decided to close the monitoring procedure in respect of Albania and to engage in post-monitoring dialogue, repeating that vetting had been a “success”.

⁴⁴ *Ibid*, paragraphs 15-16.

⁴⁵ [Joint Opinion no 963/2019](#) of the Venice Commission and the Directorate of Human Rights (DHR), of the Directorate General of Human Rights and Rule of Law (DGI) of the Council of Europe, adopted by the Venice Commission at its 120th Plenary Commission at its 120th Plenary Session (Venice, 11-12 October 2019), paragraphs 12 – 13.

⁴⁶ Expert Report on the Rule of Law Issues in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 5 December 2019, paragraphs 48-52, 53-62, 64-68, 80-81, 88 respectively. Res Publica could not find a copy of the report available, even on the [European Union’s Delegation to Bosnia and Herzegovina](#) – should the Committee require a copy, Res Publica would be more than glad to forward it.

⁴⁷ *Ibid*, § 83: “In the aftermath of the public debate “Right to Justice” civil society organisations in BiH have publicly called for vetting of judicial office holders. At this stage the experts group does not suggest vetting. Such a vetting is a measure of last resort and requires very specific conditions, as explained by the Venice Commission.”

2017 European Union commissioned *Assessment and recommendations of the Senior Experts' Group on systemic Rule of Law issues* (known as the Priebe Report), noted that there was no evidence that the legislative framework already in place was deficient and held that, despite the existence of evidence of “judiciary capture” (namely the capture of the judiciary and the prosecution by the executive power), suggestions as to the need to “cleanse” the judiciary were “unhelpful.”⁴⁸ Indeed, as noted by the North Macedonian Minister for Justice in a rule of law event organized – rather fittingly- in Tirana, it was the EU that dissuaded the North Macedonian Government from adopting a vetting along the lines of the Albanian model. In the same event, the **Kosovo** Minister of Justice also observed that it was not the EU that requested the vetting but it was a government initiative (Annex 17) – indeed, the Venice Commission was also not in favor of a vetting scheme in Kosovo along the lines of the one implemented in Albania.⁴⁹ It is recalled that even before the vetting in Albania, the Venice Commission was critical of a similar initiative in **Serbia**, where despite the existence of judges who served under an authoritarian regime (and issues of transitional justice also came into play), the Venice Commission was not convinced of the alleged need to institute a comprehensive reappointment process for all judicial officials. It noted that such a process would be extremely difficult and did not guarantee that in the end, better judges and prosecutors would be appointed. In any case, the Venice Commission highlighted the need to ensure that those subject to such a reappointment process would, among others, have the right to challenge their dismissal before an independent court.⁵⁰ Last, the EU has been against a wholesale vetting exercise in **Montenegro** as well.⁵¹

68. It would appear therefore that a vetting *cordon sanitaire* has been established around Albania, and –subject to a few exceptions that will be presented below- the international community has not, in fact, suggested vetting schemes of similar magnitude to other countries – in fact, it has sought to *prevent* them from embarking on such initiatives. This in turn could either be taken to mean that Albania’s international partners are not convinced that the vetting as implemented in Albania is a success and hence have sought to prevent it from metastasizing, or that, in the words of a legal scholar, they have silently accepted that “the country is so corrupt that, in order for it to become European, anything goes for now”.⁵² There is also a certain element of (tragic) irony in the fact that the Western Balkan countries which have not embarked on such a vetting scheme tend, according to recently published report by the Southeast European Leadership for Development and Integrity Institute (SELDI), fare better than Albania in public perception regarding whether the situation regarding combating corruption has improved: whereas in the other countries (Bosnia-Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Serbia, Montenegro, Kosovo) 40 to 50% of the respondents were optimistic (and in all countries the percentage compared to the previous survey had either increased or stayed

⁴⁸ European Union commissioned [Assessment and recommendations of the Senior Experts' Group on systemic Rule of Law issues](#), 2017, paragraphs 27, 29, 30.

⁴⁹ Venice Commission, [Opinion no 1064/2021](#), *Kosovo: Opinion on the concept paper on the vetting of judges and prosecutors and draft amendments to the Constitution*, CDL-AD(2022)011, 20 June 2022, paragraph 15.

⁵⁰ (Venice Commission), *Opinion on the Constitution of Serbia*, [CDL-AD\(2007\)004](#), paragraphs 72-73.

⁵¹ Vjesti.me, [Brussels against vetting in the judiciary](#), 22 November 2023; Balkan Insight, [Montenegro Justice Minister Insists Judicial Vetting is “State Obligation”](#), 24 September 2024; according to the article, the Minister stated that: “I know there are fears in Brussels about vetting ideas, because everyone is afraid that, due to vetting, the right to a fair trial may be threatened. If the project is well communicated, the challenges should be overcome”.

⁵² Bogdan Iancu, [Quick Fix Solutions-Anticorruption as Core / Peripheral Modality of the “Rule of Law”](#), Hague Journal on the Rule of Law, Volume 16 (2024) pages 611–642, 6 May 2024. The author rather legitimately ponders in the footnote “[...] why the anticorruption institutions should be trusted with a blank cheque if they operate in systems that are presumptively rotten to the core.”

the same), in Albania, the optimism percentage had decreased from 26% (already the lowest among all countries) in the previous survey to 20% in the current one. It is also particularly alarming that 52% of the respondents from Albania reported pressure from public officials, while 40% stated that they had bribed state officials.⁵³ While Res Publica does not suggest that it was the vetting scheme that brought forward such veritable despondency among Albanian society as to whether the scourge of corruption can be fought, such findings clearly suggest that the phenomenon of corruption in Albania is far more multi-faceted and cannot be dealt exclusively by the vetting of judges and prosecutors, which was hailed as the last hope of Albanian society against corruption.⁵⁴ The findings also suggest that the other, if any, anti-corruption measures that the Albanian Government have adopted apart from vetting, have not been effective.

69. Res Publica is aware that there are at least two vetting schemes currently under implementation, namely **Moldova** and **Ukraine**. Res Publica will not comment on the geopolitical challenges and malign influences by another state that these two countries have faced and continue to face and which clearly had an impact on the decision to embark on the vetting of judges and prosecutors, as this is beyond its ken. It will however note that both vetting schemes present significant differences to the approach adopted in the case of Albania.

70. Turning first to **Moldova**, it is noted that, while deferring to the sovereign decision of the Government, the Venice Commission cautioned against the adoption of a full-blown vetting scheme and suggested making full use of already available mechanisms, noting also that perceptions of corruption in the judiciary do not necessarily warrant a vetting process. Should however the Government proceed with vetting, the Commission considered that the assessment criteria under the vetting should be the “same as those already in force concerning the disciplinary liability and performance evaluation of judges” (at § 50). The Venice Commission also indicated that the evaluation bodies should be composed of a substantial number of members with a *judicial* background and was critical of the possibility of the members of the public making complaints about the judges under evaluation.⁵⁵ The vetting model ultimately adopted appears to be in conformity with the recommendations of the Venice Commission. Interestingly enough, in the first phase of the vetting, the screening of the candidates for the vetting bodies was conducted by the Pre-Vetting Commission (as opposed to the Parliamentary Sub-Committee in Albania); its task was to vet the candidates for the self-governing bodies of the judges and prosecutors (Superior Council of Magistracy (SCM) or the Superior Council of Prosecutors (SCP); failed candidates could appeal to the Supreme Court of Justice, which in many cases overturned the decisions of the Pre-Vetting Commission. Moreover, there is no body similar to the IMO; Moldova’s international partners nominated three out of the six members of the Pre-Vetting Commission (it is of note that these members were appointed by the Moldovan authorities from a list of candidates forwarded to them by the international partners, rather than “imposed” by Moldova’s international partners). Following the establishment of the SCM and SCP, three new

⁵³ Euronews Albania, *Report: Albania has the highest bribery rates in the Western Balkans*, 3 October 2024.

The SELDI regional anticorruption report entitled *Breaking the anticorruption deadlock in the Western Balkans*, was published on 1 October 2024.

⁵⁴ It should be noted that the dismissals of former SAC members L.D. and A.H., as well as the issue of the IQC staff retreat, received scant attention in national media and did not lead to any debates regarding their implications; Res Publica finds this particularly alarming as it suggests that both the media and the public have effectively abandoned all hope as to the positive change the vetting can bring and merely record and read about such developments.

⁵⁵ Opinion no. 966/2019, *Interim Joint Opinion on the Draft Law on the Reform of the Supreme Court of Justice and the Prosecutor’s Office*, [CDL-AD\(2019\)020](#), paragraphs 46- 47, 50, 55, 71 respectively.

vetting commissions were formed (the vetting commission for Supreme Court Judges and two vetting commissions for high-ranking judges and prosecutors). Unlike the Pre-Vetting Commission, these vetting commissions are tasked with preparing evaluation reports for the assessee; it will be up to the reformed SCM and SCP to ultimately decide whether to accept the respective commission's evaluation report or not. The commissions (and the assessee) have the right to appeal the SCM's / SCP's decisions to the Supreme Court of Justice.⁵⁶

71. Res Publica notes that the Moldovan vetting model strikes a far better balance between fighting corruption in the judiciary and upholding the rights of the assessee than the Albanian one; the vetting is being undertaken by the respective self-regulatory bodies (and not by parallel ones) whose members are judges and prosecutors who have been vetted and appointed by a commission with the participation of Moldova's international partners (unlike in the Albanian case where the members were appointed by Parliament, a crucial shortcoming that undermined the entire process). It is also important that there are different bodies responsible for the vetting of judges and prosecutors (unlike Albania) who face different challenges in their work. Last, assessee in Moldova have the right to appeal, albeit on specific grounds, to the reformed Supreme Court of Justice – unlike assessee in Albania. Indeed, as noted above, the only element that the Moldovan vetting scheme appears to have borrowed from its Albanian counterpart is that of the “financial amnesty” regarding unjustified assets. While admittedly the relevant threshold is in principle lower in the Moldovan vetting than the Albanian one, this makes little difference in practice since Article 61(1) Vetting Act has never, to Res Publica's best knowledge, been applied to confirm or dismiss an assessee.

72. The situation regarding the vetting in Ukraine is more complicated; nevertheless, already from the first vetting scheme that was implemented, assessee had a right to file an appeal against a decision issued by the High Qualification Commission of Judges (HQCJ), part of the High Council of Justice, but also against decisions of the High Council of Justice or of the Parliament or President of Ukraine, before the Higher Administrative Court (*Oleksandr Volkov v. Ukraine*, no. 21722/11, § 62, 9 January 2013). In other words, the HQCJ were not amenable to an appeal to a special court having competence to hear only vetting cases but to a court belonging to and being an integral part of the judiciary.

73. The current vetting scheme under implementation in Ukraine, while rather more complicated than the Moldova one, provides for similar guarantees. Thus the members of the HQCJ were appointed by the Selection Commission, consisting of six members, three of which were serving or retired judges nominated by the Council of Judges of Ukraine and the other three nominated by Ukraine's international partners.⁵⁷ The HQCJ is assisted by the Public Integrity Council (PIC), which consist of 20 members drawn from NGOs, lawyers, journalists;⁵⁸ their role is to draw up an opinion as to whether a judge or a judicial candidate

⁵⁶ The above are based on a very useful summary of the Moldovan vetting scheme in comparison to the Albania one by Dr(c) Andrea Mazelliu, [Navigating the Vetting Process in Moldova: a comparative analysis with the Albanian model – Quis custodiet upsos custodes?](#), Freedom House, May 2024. Regarding the right to appeal, see [Law No. 252/2023 On the external evaluation of judges and prosecutors and amendments of some regulatory acts](#), Article 19.

⁵⁷ Law [On the Judiciary and the Status of Judges](#), Article 50. Admittedly, local NGOs were critical of the appointment of the members by the Council of Judges, considering that the entire process was rather *pro forma*. They nevertheless were in favor of the inclusion of international experts in the Selection Commission, calling for the extension of their two-year mandate. See DEJURE, [Analytical Report: 4 years, 2 laws, 16 members: how the new composition of the High Qualification Commission of Judges of Ukraine was selected](#), September 2023.

⁵⁸ Law [On the Judiciary and the Status of Judges](#), Article 87.

meets the criteria of professional ethics and integrity. Should PIC consider that they do not meet them, then their decision can be reversed by the HQCJ only by means of a 2/3 vote. An assessee disagreeing with the HQCJ can challenge their opinion, on a limited number of grounds, before the Supreme Court.⁵⁹

74. Once again, it is seen that in Ukraine international partners are more engaged in the day to day running of the vetting than their counterparts in Albania. What is more important for present purposes is that, just like in Moldova, assessees in Ukraine can challenge before a court that is part of the judicial machinery a HQCJ decision to not confirm them in office, thus making the Albanian vetting an outlier in that respect, also raising the legitimate question as to why a similar set up was not adopted in Albania – even though, as noted above, the Venice Commission was in favor of a right to challenge a decision issued by SAC’s predecessor before the Constitutional Court.

VI. Assessing the Albanian Government’s commitment to the rule of law

75. Res Publica maintains that vetting schemes do not take place in a vacuum; it is therefore crucial to review the wider context in which such schemes are adopted with a view to assessing both the need for their adoption as well as, and perhaps more importantly, the modalities for their conception and implementation, particularly since such reforms present the potential for the executive to further increase its influence over the judiciary, as noted by the Venice Commission in its quote at the beginning of this submission. Furthermore, as also noted by the Court, constitutional safeguards of the independence and impartiality of the judiciary do not suffice unless they are ingrained in everyday administrative attitudes and practices (*Agrokompleks v. Ukraine*, no. 23465/03, § 136, 6 October 2011).

76. It will therefore be instructive to briefly examine how the Albanian Government respond to judgments issued by or proceedings before courts whose integrity is beyond reproach. Starting with the **Kosovo Specialist Chambers**, and while speaking before the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe (PACE), the Albanian Prime Minister expressed his criticism of the PACE report compiled by Mr. Dick Marty into alleged war crimes committed by the Kosovo Liberation Army, suggesting that the Chambers were founded on false pretenses, drawing a retort by Mr Cilevičs that “The matter is not in our hands, it is in the hands of the judiciary, and we do respect the independence of the judiciary in this House”.⁶⁰

77. Turning to the **World Bank International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID)** decision in Case no. ARB/15/28 *Hydro and Others v. Albania*, it was the Albanian Prime Minister again who bluntly stated that the Government would not execute that judgment.⁶¹ Indeed, the Albanian Government even toyed with the idea of establishing a local arbitration court.⁶²

⁵⁹ Law *On the Judiciary and the Status of Judges*, Article 88.

⁶⁰ PACE, Minutes of the [opening of the sitting No 31](#), Wednesday 12 October 2022, afternoon.

⁶¹ Reporter.al, [Rama: Qeveria do paguajë inceneratorët, por jo Francesco Becchettin](#), [Rama: the Government will pay for the incinerators but not for Francesco Becchetti] 30 December 2021; for a more graphic expression of the Albanian Prime Minister’s resolve in not abiding by the ICSID decision, see Gazeta Shqip, [Gjyqi me Becchetin, Rama: Ai marifetçiu, me Metën dhe Berishën do marrin atë që s’thuhet](#), [Trial with Becchetti, Rama: That swindler, with Meta and Berisha, will get what is not said], 7 April 2021.

⁶² BalkanInsight, [Albania Moves to Establish Local Arbitration Court to Replace ICSID](#), 21 April 2023.

78. The Albanian Government's attitude towards the **Court** is equally concerning: an Albanian official tried to exert pressure on a former judge in respect of Albania, drawing a reaction by the Court which considered such actions "inappropriate".⁶³ One could consider equally inappropriate the Albanian Prime Minister's statement that he would not abide by the Court's judgment in *Sharxhi and Others v. Albania* (no. 10613/16, 11 January 2016).⁶⁴ At least the Government are consistent: as indicated by the applicants' recent submission to the Committee of Ministers, the "Ministry of Finance and Economy persistently "exclude(s) from the reporting of outstanding obligations the state's obligations from Arbitration Court and European Court of Human Rights decisions"⁶⁵ - in other words, the Albanian Government is not planning on executing any of these judgments anytime soon. Res Publica will merely note that such statements have been held to be "clearly in contradiction with the basic tenets of the rule of law" (*Sabuncu and Others v. Turkey*, no. 23199/17, § 225 *in finem*, 10 November 2020), while deliberately disregarding a binding judicial decision "can only be characterised as blatant defiance of the rule of law" (*Advance Pharma sp. z o.o v. Poland* (no. 1469/20, § 334, 3 February 2022).

79. Admittedly, it could be argued that the failure to execute the aforementioned judgments is not politically motivated, as evidenced by the European Commission's finding in its 2024 *Rule of Law Report on Albania*, on 1 January 2024, Albania had 24 leading judgments pending implementation; its rate of leading judgments issued in the last 10 years that remained pending was 96% (with one judgment pending implementation for 10 years), while the number of leading judgments pending implementation was increasing and by 1 July 2024 had increased to 30. The judgments whose implementation was pending concerned mostly the non-enforcement of final court decisions ordering the reinstatement of dismissed public servants in the civil sector and property issues⁶⁶ - clearly not as high profile as the ICSID and *Sharxhi and Others* judgments yet rather indicative (particularly the ones regarding the failure to reinstate dismissed public servants). According to the latest statistics from the Department for the Execution of Judgments of the European Court of Human Rights, as of 20 September 2024, there are now 31 leading judgments the implementation of which is pending; Albania's percentage of such cases is 63%, the third highest after Russian Federations (74%) and Azerbaijan (73%); it is of some interest that the respective percentages for Bosnia and Herzegovina and North Macedonia are much lower than those of Albania (25% and 24% respectively).⁶⁷ Regardless of whether the failure to execute some judgments might or might not be politically motivated therefore, there is a particularly acute problem regarding the execution of Court judgments in general; moreover, the fact that some of the judgments are executed whereas others not leads to the conclusion that over all these years the Albanian Government quite simply picks and chooses which judgments it will execute.

80. In light of the above, it should come as no surprise that the Albanian Government consistently fails to abide even by domestic court judgments, including judgments issued by

⁶³ BalkanInsight, [ECHR Chides Albania's "Inappropriate" Attempt to Sway Ruling](#), 30 August 2018.

⁶⁴ Council of Europe Committee of Ministers, [Communication from the applicant in the case of Sharxhi and Others v. Albania](#), DH-DD (2018)1206, dated 28 November 2018

⁶⁵ Council of Europe Committee of Ministers, [Communication from the applicant in the case of Sharxhi and Others v. Albania](#), DH-DD (2024)936, dated 20 August 2024.

⁶⁶ European Commission, [Commission Staff Working Document – 2024 Rule of Law Report, Country Chapter on the rule of law situation in Albania](#), SWD(2024)828 final, 24 July 2024, pages 22-23.

⁶⁷ Country factsheets, [Albania](#).

the Albanian Constitutional Court.⁶⁸ Or that, with the support of the major opposition party, it enacted an amnesty law that according to SPAK benefitted 100 persons, 40 of whom had been convicted for exercising illegal influence and were pardoned, while another 60 who had been convicted for criminal offenses of corruption, violations of equality in tenders or abuse of office received reduced sentences.⁶⁹ Sometimes undermining the rule of law requires bipartisan political support.

VII. A vetting “bon pour l’Albanie”? Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusions

81. Res Publica considers that the extensive reference to different aspects of the vetting scheme currently under implementation in Albania was necessary in order to place its findings regarding the execution of the *Besnik Cani* and *Sevdari* judgments in their proper context and formulate more fit-for-purpose recommendations.

82. Regarding the former judgment, Res Publica contends that it has presented conclusive evidence, based on SAC’s jurisprudence, of SAC’s purposeful failure to abide by the Court’s judgment, as well as of the Albanian Government’s misguided arguments – rejected by SAC itself – as to the possibility of having the case reopened before SAC.

83. Regarding the latter judgment, Res Publica asserts that, despite the Court’s holding, assessee cannot request the reopening of proceedings before SAC unless they have secured a Court judgment to that effect. Moreover, SAC continues to ignore the Court’s main ratio in that case that concerns the proper assessment of the licit origin of unjustified income and the corresponding application of a key safeguard for assessee, namely Article 61(1) Vetting Act. Even though she was eventually reinstated, the fact that her request for reopening of the proceedings was heard largely by the same SAC members who originally dismissed her, coupled with the fact that she did not have at her disposal any effective remedies that would have allowed her to ask for those SAC members’ recusal, suggest that her reinstatement, while fortuitous to her and to the Prosecution Service, fell short of the fair trial guarantees under Article 6.

84. While the above would be enough to amply support the conclusion that the Albanian Government and SAC are effectively *refusing* to abide by the Court’s judgments, Res Publica in the present submission has sought to establish that this failure was all but unavoidable, given the characteristics of the vetting scheme as conceived, designed and implemented. Contrary to what the Albanian Government and SAC claim, neither the Venice Commission nor the Constitutional Court endorsed the vetting scheme; the former explicitly and repeatedly called for the inclusion a crucial safeguard (namely the possibility of recourse to the Constitutional Court) which was surreptitiously dropped from the final draft, while the latter explicitly stated that it could not review the vetting scheme’s compliance with the Constitution.⁷⁰ Similarly, entrusting a

⁶⁸ Ibid, footnote 195. According to the report, the Albanian Government have failed to execute at least six Constitutional Court judgments, all issued *post-2022* (i.e. from the fully vetted Constitutional Court).

⁶⁹ Reporter.al, [SPAK: Amnistia penale shkurtoi dënimin e dhjetëra zyrtarëve të korruptuar](#), [SPAK: the penal amnesty shortened the sentence of dozens of corrupt officials], 30 April 2024; the same article is available in English at Voxnews.al (albeit with a different title), [SP-Rithemelimi/ SPAK cooperation: Criminal amnesty shortened the sentence of dozens of corrupt officials](#), 30 April 2024.

⁷⁰ Sadly, the Constitutional Court has not, to date, carried out any substantive review of the vetting scheme’s constitutionality. Thus constitutional complaints involving vetting issues lodged with it since 2017, even those

Parliament not known for its members' moral integrity with unfettered discretion in appointing, on a basis of a political agreement, the vetting bodies' members by means of a pro-forma selection (with candidates asked to self-declare if they had faced disciplinary proceedings in the past) and an appointment process that was completed in record time (a fact that should have made the proponents of vetting pause for thought, rather than rejoice over meeting the unduly tight timeframes) must have been considered from the outset as a rather bad idea. Nor was this the only such idea; restricting SAC's jurisdiction – by means of a constitutional provision no less – thus effectively undermining its character as a court, while calling upon it to play a crucial role in establishing the rule of law, strikes Res Publica as highly contradictory.

85. At the same time, Albanian's international partners appear not only to have signed off on the above, they have also failed to use their leverage to address some of the most glaring shortcomings, even though their refusal to support similar schemes in neighboring countries or their support of vetting schemes that present marked differences to Albanian model seems to suggest that they are all too aware of the latter's failings. Rather, they seem content to leave vetting run its course, oblivious to the havoc it is wreaking in the Albanian judiciary. Res Publica is not referring primarily to the huge backlog of all domestic courts; it is far more concerned by another, far more insidious side effect. If unfairly dismissed judges and prosecutors have at least the option of addressing their grievance to the Court and eventually possibly being reinstated, what happens to unfairly *confirmed* judges and prosecutors who now have the vetting's stamp of approval? Given that they were confirmed despite the more onerous procedural requirements under the vetting scheme, how likely is it that the ordinary disciplinary proceedings will be a sufficient deterrent for them in the future? Or how certain can one be that the members of the vetting bodies, most of them with scant legal skills in the highly complex field of disciplinary proceedings against judicial officials and themselves unlawfully appointed, will have confirmed in duty the right people? In at least one case, the IMO Observers considered that this was not done – yet failed to do anything meaningful about it. In fact, and in what Res Publica can only consider as a highly ironic twist, it was the applicants in *Besnik Cani* and *Sevdari* who, with their insistence, ended up “vetting” the former SAC members L.D. and A.H, bringing about their dismissal. The irony becomes more poignant if one also takes into account that, had they not been dismissed, Messrs. L.D. and A.H. would become Appeals Court judges following the end of their mandate as SAC members (Annex 1, Article 166(6) Status of Judges and Prosecutors Act) – an appointment that, adding insult to injury, was meant to act as guarantee of their judicial independence by ensuring that their judicial mandate was not temporary.

86. The above findings by Res Publica should be tempered by its acknowledgment that the Court has yet to pronounce itself regarding many issues that were presented above, such as for example the lawfulness of the appointment of vetting bodies members - an issue that, it bears repeating, it did not examine in *Xhoxhaj* and subsequent cases. As such, Res Publica's arguments (regarding, for example, the potential outcome of applying the *Ástráðsson* test or its *Reczkowicz* variant) can be considered as unsubstantiated at worst or as premature at best. Nevertheless, Res Publica strongly believes that the Court's extensive jurisprudence on these issues makes it possible to anticipate, with a reasonable degree of accuracy, the Court's findings should it be seised of these issues. By way of example, and while deferring to the Court's eventual judgment in a case raising this issue, Res Publica can hardly see how the

going beyond the express limitations of Article A of the Annex that “partially” divest the Constitutional Court of jurisdiction, have been rejected at the three-judge selection stage, not even passing to a plenary hearing, with the Constitutional Court citing only decision no. 2/2017, approving the vetting law in the abstract.

extraordinary nature of vetting can legitimize a palpably unlawful appointment process left entirely to Parliament's discretion in appointing the vetting bodies *directly*, in light of the Court's judgment in a series of Polish cases in which, while not challenging the judicial reform *per se*, it took issue with the Government's *indirect* influence on the appointment of judges.

87. With the above in mind, Res Publica can offer a tentative answer to the issues raised by the two quotes in the beginning of the present submission. While it cannot give a definitive answer as to whether the vetting in Albania was instrumentalised in order to allow the executive to capture the judiciary, it should be borne in mind that there are numerous and persistent concerns about different kinds of state capture in Albania, and that it is rather illogical to consider that state capture is limited only to particular fields. A joint Transparency International / Institute for Democracy and Mediation report identified nine-tailor made laws serving rather identifiable business concerns, with the authors being critical of various aspects of the law drafting and adoption processes, noting that they lacked transparency and were often rushed through Parliament. The report also observed that state capture had increased significantly in Albania between 2008 – 2019, despite EU-sponsored reforms to establish a professional public administration.⁷¹ According to the 2024 SELDI regional anticorruption report: “The decisive wins of incumbent strongmen in Serbia and Albania have resulted not in anticorruption breakthroughs but in higher state capture risks and more control over the media”.⁷² Similarly, according to the recently published *Global Organised Crime Index 2023*, criminal networks in Albania are “highly embedded in local and regional level structures”, cooperate with the police and receive political protection, while their members have reportedly been appointed to political positions; in return, they use their power to influence elections.⁷³ It is therefore not entirely surprising that the recently appointed (and “vetted”) director of the Albanian Police has had his mobile phone seized in the context of an investigation by SPAK regarding suspected leaks of confidential information to an organized crime gang.⁷⁴

88. The answer to the issue raised by the second quote is easier: as has been seen above, there *are* double standards when it comes to assessing the liability of members of the vetting bodies and assessees; the former, appointed on the basis of a procedure tainted by numerous shortcomings which did not ensure that they met the relevant qualifications (let alone that they have the requisite moral integrity), are immune from challenges of their appointment (even after it has been established that they were unlawfully appointed) and will continue to serve unless they commit, or are found to have committed, a crime. Moreover, under Article 17(1) Vetting Act (Annex 1) only IQC members themselves and IMO Observers can initiate disciplinary proceedings against IQC members; it is rather unlikely that an IQC observer, appointed by means of a palpably deficient procedure, would request disciplinary proceedings against one of their colleagues, appointed on the basis of the same procedure. Shortcomings in their appointment process will not render their decision null and void (as is the case with ordinary judges, regardless of the time of their appointment; *Besnik Cani*, op. cit., §102), thus leading already to situations where assessees who were dismissed by panels on with either

⁷¹ [Deconstructing State Capture in Albania, An Examination of Grand Corruption Cases and Tailor-Made Laws from 2008 to 2020](#), 30 March 2021, page 34.

⁷² SELDI report, op. cit., page 14.

⁷³ [Country Profile: Albania](#), Chapter 7, Criminal Actors.

⁷⁴ BalkanInsight, [Before he's even started, Albania's new police chief has phone seized in probe](#), 2 October 2024. According to the article, when queried, both the Interior Ministry and the Prime Minister's office responded that the new police director had been fully vetted (“the shortlisting process to become the new police chief has been a success, while stressing that the candidates had been shortlisted after collecting the opinion of many institutions, including SPAK”).

former SAC members L.D. and A.H. – or both!- sat, cannot reopen the proceedings and have to endure both the ignominy of being branded as corrupt (for clearly, given the smear campaign against the judiciary before and during the vetting, Albanian society considers dismissed judges as corrupt) while having been dismissed by usurper judges. As to IMO, it has repeatedly shown that it too continues to ignore the Court’s judgments and is reluctant to take *any* disciplinary measure against vetting bodies’ members, as seen by the lack of any follow-up in the cases of IQC member A.F.V., their comments on SAC’s decision in the case of assessee G.H. and the *soliciting* of a donation by the IQC. As if this were not enough, they are tasked with *reviewing* the skills and integrity of the assessees and passing judgment on them. Similarly, while assessees are subject to a particularly – and often excessively and in violation of the Vetting Act - rigorous review of different aspects of their career and choices in cases they dealt with or the company they kept, IQC/SAC members are unlikely to face disciplinary charges, even in cases where they openly demand favors and solicit donations from wealthy businesspersons. One is left wondering as to what would the outcome be if the members of the vetting bodies – or, indeed, the IMO Observers- were re-evaluated based on the vetting scheme and the case law they have developed to date.

Recommendations for general and individual measures in the context of the execution of the Besnik Cani and Sevdari judgments

89. Another reason why this lengthy presentation of the shortcomings of the vetting process was necessary is because it also has a bearing on Res Publica’s recommendations. Given the structural nature of these shortcomings, it is all but unavoidable that some of the recommendations will be structural in character.

90. Starting from recommendations regarding **general measures** at the domestic level that are clearly necessary, given that the violations in *Besnik Cani* and *Sevdari* affect a large number of people (*Yüksel Yalçınkaya v. Türkiye* [GC], no. 15669/20, § 416, 26 September 2023), Res Publica’s first recommendation concerns an issue that might not have a direct bearing on vetting proceedings but is of significant symbolic value and concerns the abolition of SAC’s ultimate disciplinary jurisdiction over all judicial officials (including recently appointed and vetted Constitutional Court judges) and other officials of the judiciary under Article 179 § 7 of the Constitution (Annex 1). Res Publica can ascertain no valid reason why SAC should have such jurisdiction over vetted judicial officials, or officials appointed after the launching of the vetting. Moreover, such a measure could also forestall applications by said judicial officials against SAC final decisions in disciplinary proceedings against them; clearly, applicants in such cases could use the same arguments as applicants in vetting proceedings to complaint about the unlawful appointment of SAC members.

91. In practical terms, the most pressing general measure would consist of the establishment of a body tasked with reviewing challenges regarding the unlawful appointment of vetting bodies’ members. For reasons that were presented at length at above – but also on the basis of SAC’s self-professed impossibility of fulfilling that role-, Res Publica, echoing the Venice Commission’s original recommendation, considers that a chamber of the Constitutional Court should be assigned with that role, as well as the role of reviewing requests for the reopening of proceedings under all grounds set out in Article 494 Code of Civil Procedure. This will not only afford assessees a domestic remedy, it will also hopefully stem the flow of cases to the Court as well as allow the Court to direct, on the basis of the principle of subsidiarity, cases currently pending before it and raising such issues to the body to be designated; such retroactive

effect is amply justified, in Res Publica's opinion, on compelling public interest grounds (*Beshiri and Others v. Albania* (dec), no. 29026/06, §228, 7 May 2020; *Société Provitel Saint-Georges et J. Emery* (dec), no. 29437/08, 9 November 2010). Such a measure would be in conformity with those adopted by the Icelandic and Polish Governments in the context of execution of the respective judgments. It would moreover be necessary for another reason: as noted above, the remaining SAC member at the end of its mandate will have the right to be appointed automatically as Appeals Court judges, at a time when the lawfulness of their original appointment has never been reviewed. It is therefore crucial for a truly independent body, enjoying full jurisdiction, to be given the possibility to review their appointment before they join the Appeals Court.

92. Res Publica also considers that vetting bodies should be directed to fully apply (after, if need be, the provision of remedial training to their members on key tenets of the Vetting Act) the vetting legislation and in particular Article 61(1) Vetting Act, in line with the Court's direction in *Sevdari* and the dissenting SAC member's and IMO Observer's opinion in the same case. At the same time, the Albanian Government should proceed to review the cases that have been communicated to it. Should it appear that the only reason for the assessee's dismissal was related to their assets and provided it is clear that the unjustified income was not of illicit origin and that it does not surpass 100% of the assessee's lawful income / property, then the Albanian Government should either enter into friendly settlement proceedings with the assessee or, by means of unilateral declaration, seek to dispose of the cases (*Kunić and Others v. Bosnia and Herzegovina*, nos 68955/12 and 15 others, § 35, 14 November 2017). This would allow for the applicants' swift reinstatement (*Sorbalo c. Moldova*, op. cit, § 58) and filling of the numerous vacancies by experienced judges and prosecutors, rather than recent graduates from the School of Magistrates, whose training – as mentioned in the EU Rule of law report- cannot be considered adequate, while the School itself (among the professors of which are assesseees were dismissed during the vetting) has been at the center of criticism for the holding of examinations.⁷⁵ It is of some importance that the School of Magistrates has *lowered* the average grade for qualifying, and that the High Judicial Council also lowered the qualifying grade for judicial assistants.⁷⁶

94 Res Publica stresses that the above measures are necessary not only in order to safeguard the assesseees' rights, they are also crucial in stemming the flow of repetitive cases to the Court. They are also necessary in order to restore the tarnished integrity of the vetting scheme.

95. Turning to **individual measures**, and regarding the *Besnik Cani* judgment, it would appear that the only feasible short-term solution is to acknowledge that, given SAC's impossibility to form a fresh panel to review his request for reopening, the only body that can review it in the merits is the High Prosecutorial Council, all the more since, as argued above, SAC's original decision ought to be considered null and void and consequently cannot be reopened. To hold otherwise would amount to penalizing him for the failure of the drafters of the vetting scheme to foresee such an eventuality.

96. Regarding the *Sevdari* judgment, even though she was ultimately reinstated (by means of a procedure that did not comply with the fair trial guarantees set out in Article 6), there is no

⁷⁵ Op. cit, pages 7-8.

⁷⁶ Reporter.al, [Pas Magjistraturës, edhe KLGJ ndryshon kriterin e mesatares për ndihmësit ligjorë](#) [After the School of Magistrates, the High Judicial Council also changes the average grade [criterion] for judicial assistants], 7 February 2024.

information in the Albanian Government's action plan as to whether she was awarded any pecuniary and non-pecuniary damages; the award of such damages should be prompt and be made *proprio motu*, without relying on a filing of a request by the applicant to that end. By way of example, in a similar case in Moldova the competent court which ordered the applicant's reinstatement also ordered, by means of the same judgment, the awarding of pecuniary damages consisting of the unpaid salaries (*Sorbalo c. Moldova*, op. cit, §19, 52); in addition to being fair, such a measure could also alleviate, even if slightly, the Albanian courts' backlog. Turning to non-pecuniary damages, while Res Publica does not consider that they should have a punitive nature, it believes they should reflect the severe mental anguish that the applicants experience, both before and during the implementation of the vetting scheme, having become (together with their colleagues) the object of a smear campaign, an example of which being the Albanian Prime Minister's announcement of the adoption of the so-called anti-KCK (*Kap Çatë Kapësh*, "grab what you can") package against serving judicial officials who had yet to be evaluated but who allegedly abused their position for private gain, noting rather immoderately, given the extent of organized crime in Albania, that they are "the most dangerous criminal organization that currently operates in Albania".⁷⁷

97. In addition to the recommendations outlined above, a more important one that can hardly be indicated, let alone supervised, by the Committee of Ministers is that of fostering a culture of respect for domestic international and domestic court judgments. This is clearly the responsibility of the Albanian Government: like charity, respect for the rule of law begins at home. Making serious efforts to execute the Court's judgments – instead of adding to its workload- would be an important step in that direction.

Respectfully submitted

14 October 2024

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Executive Director
Res Publica

⁷⁷ Exit.al, [Rama once again deflects attention by calling judiciary "the most dangerous criminal organization](#), 6 November 2019.